

Control Room of the Future (framework) / D4.1

WP4.1, T4.1

Authors: Thomas Lokken (YWR), Pieter Gebraad (YWR), Samuel Kainz (TUM), Abhinav Anand (TUM), Adrien Guilloré (TUM), Carlo L. Bottasso (TUM), Niclas Jacob (SOW), Marian Albers (SOW), Riccardo Riva (DTU), Andreas Bechmann (DTU), Tim Dammann (TUD), Daan van der Hoek (TUD)

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents strategies for assessing and optimising wind farm control, integrating the latest models of the SUDOCO project. The integrated decision-making framework combines open-source models of wind farm aerodynamics, turbine health, economic revenue, and environmental impact. The framework contains two strategies - The economic lifetime-aware wind farm control and the desirability approach - for integrating the models into the *Control Room of the Future*. Both strategies support operators and developers in evaluating the business case of advanced wind farm control, using performance metrics that balance economic and environmental value. Environmental value can currently only be computed in a post-processing step and is not directly incorporated into the decision-making framework. This will be included in the optimised framework in work package 4.2.

The framework includes: an engineering wake model with verified integrated farm control capability, load and reliability surrogate models, economic value functions, and environmental value functions. Together, these enable both static and dynamic evaluation of control strategies, enabling lifetime-aware, economically robust, and environmentally conscious decision-making.

Key results from this report include:

- Linear functions for quick economic evaluation of operations & maintenance.
- Requirements, potential, and scope of including floating wind in the *Control Room of the Future*.
- Integration of the Helix control technique with the wind farm modelling tool, PyWake.
- Continued improvement and applicability of the environmental value function within the scope of the *Control Room of the Future*.
- A lifetime-aware wind farm control strategy that combines state-of-the-art tools for optimal wind farm performance over its lifetime.

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- Holistic wind farm control optimisation using the desirability approach. An approach to value functions, irrespective of the economic value of the objective function.
- A graphical user interface that ensures that the desirability approach is available to operators with limited Python experience.

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1 Introduction

Operators can pursue different objectives for their wind farms, and these objectives can shift over the farm's lifetime. Such changes may be driven by market fluctuations, evolving policy requirements, or the adoption of new technological options. This report introduces the latest integrated tools designed to support operators in making optimised decisions for the future of wind farm operation.

Most of the tools presented here have been developed within the SUDOCO project. They represent the state of the art in holistic wind farm control and are specifically designed to support the *Control Room of the Future*. Unlike many existing tools, these solutions provide the operator with the flexibility to prioritize and adjust control objectives over the wind farm's lifetime.

1.1 Wind farm control techniques

This section reviews several wind farm control techniques: wake steering, the Helix approach, and axial induction control.

Wake steering involves deliberately yawing upstream turbines — turning them slightly away from the incoming wind — to redirect their wakes away from downstream machines. This reduces the negative impact of slower, turbulent air and can increase total plant output while lowering fatigue loads (Fleming et al., 2017; Howland et al., 2019). In practice, this means harvesting more energy, extending turbine lifetimes, and reducing maintenance costs.

The Helix approach introduces dynamic motion to turbine operation (Frederik et al., 2020). Instead of producing a static, slow-moving wake, turbines create a helical flow pattern that mixes more effectively with surrounding high-speed wind. This accelerates wake recovery, enabling downstream turbines to regain higher wind speeds and boosting their output (Korb et al., 2023). Unlike conventional methods, the Helix approach stays close to normal operating limits while adding periodic variation. Its main trade-off is the potential for increased structural fatigue, which must be weighed against the performance gains.

Axial induction control works by adjusting the pitch angles of upstream turbines to capture slightly less energy, leaving more wind energy available for turbines downwind (Machielse et al., 2007). When these pitch settings are optimised as a function of wind direction, the total energy yield of the farm can be increased (van der Hoek et al., 2019). This technique highlights the balance between individual turbine output and collective wind farm efficiency.

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1.2 The Control Room of the Future

The *Control Room of the Future* provides a flexible design space that enables present and future operators to combine state-of-the-art tools that communicate seamlessly with one another. This communication, or coupling, between engineering models is central to identifying the most suitable control strategy.

Such a holistic control room focuses on optimising wind farm economic value, lifetime extension, and environmental gains. Ultimately, however, the definition of “optimal” depends on the operator’s priorities. Therefore, the *Control Room of the Future* must always allow tunable parameters and adaptable strategies rather than imposing a single, fixed solution.

Figure 1.1 illustrates the SUDOCO framework presented in this report. Operators can switch between wake models, choose from three distinct value functions, and apply alternative control strategies within a single integrated environment.

Figure 1.1: The framework of the *Control Room of the Future* design.

The control strategies described here are the result of a productive collaboration. Each strategy utilises the available value functions in different ways, resulting in variations in control room design. Yet the underlying design principles remain the same, widening the range of options available to operators while ensuring access to the full suite of value functions developed in SUDOCO. This structure also forms the structure of this report.

1.3 Outline of the report

Chapter 2 covers the Load & Health Models, beginning with integrated surrogate models and their coupling with dynamic simulations. Special attention is given to

adaptations for floating wind and the use of structural health monitoring, providing a foundation for lifetime-aware control strategies.

Chapter 3 presents the Economic Value Functions, which quantify the costs and benefits of operating a wind farm under different strategies. This includes models for operations and maintenance costs, regular and unplanned operations, and the detailed treatment of component replacement, failure, and degradation.

Chapter 4 explores the Environmental Value Objectives. It introduces how environmental considerations can be quantified and integrated directly into control decisions.

Chapter 5 discusses the Control Strategies of the Future. It details two prototype approaches — the economic lifetime-aware control and the desirability approach — showing how they incorporate the value functions and load models presented in earlier chapters.

Finally, Chapter 6 contains the conclusion of the work presented in the previous chapters.

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2 Load & Health Models

The *Control Room of the Future* includes objectives beyond purely power maximization. To consider structural fatigue loading in the optimisations of wind farm control, the development of fast but accurate reduced-order models is necessary. Determining fatigue loadings typically requires running long aero-servo-elastic simulations including dynamic wake effects. But this is unfeasible as part of an optimisation framework. For this reason, reduced-order load surrogate models were developed as part of the SUDOCO project. This chapter gives an overview of the fatigue surrogate models, describes the coupling with static and dynamic models, and discusses the potential extension for floating wind energy.

2.1 Integrated surrogate models

Several complementary approaches of load surrogate models have been developed as part of the SUDOCO project. The details of the methodology and the results of different types of load surrogate approaches and architectures are described in details in the Deliverable D2.1 (Guilloré et al., 2025).

Across various methodological choices and parametric studies, the main findings were that there is a finite complexity that is sufficient to obtain converged performances for a general wind turbine load surrogate model. A finite number of training cases, a finite number of wind turbulent seeds and a finite number of inputs to characterize the complex dynamic local inflow experienced by a turbine are enough to obtain a converged load surrogate model. Details on these studies and different kinds of surrogate models of the SUDOCO project can be found in Shaler et al. (2022), Liew et al. (2024a), and Guilloré et al. (2024).

The load surrogate models are data-driven functions that predict fatigue loadings, most typically in terms of Damage Equivalent Loads (DELs) of various structural components, while it can also be other structural metrics. After training, the computational cost of the surrogates is negligible with respect to PyWake simulation of the flow within the farm, making them suitable for optimization problems. The inputs of the surrogate need to characterize the 10-minute average (towards “steady-state”) local inflow that a rotor experiences as well as the spatio-temporal dependency of this inflow (through various points across the rotor and the use of turbulence intensities in addition to mean wind speeds). The surrogates also have as inputs some parameters characterizing the control mode (such as yaw misalignment for wake steering, amplitude and frequency for Helix control, or curtailment

level for induction control). This allows the surrogates to capture the variations of fatigue loadings by local inflow (including wake effects) and by control actions.

A variety of turbulent seeds needs to be run in order to reach statistical convergence of both the inputs and the outputs of the surrogates. Based on findings in Guilloré et al. (2025), 12 turbulent seeds seem to be a good choice for good location-agnostic load surrogates.

Deliverable D2.1 (Guilloré et al., 2025) focused on parametric studies on the best ways to build load surrogate models. It included results from several open-source wind turbine models (the IEA 3.4MW, the IEA 15MW, and the IEA 22MW turbines). Within the *Control Room of the Future* of the SUDOCO project, we will use the IEA 22MW reference wind turbine (Zahle et al., 2024) to represent the next generation of very large offshore wind turbines.

Based on the findings of Guilloré et al. (2025), a new load surrogate model was developed for the IEA 22MW reference turbine, to be applied specifically for the study cases of the *Control Room of the Future*. The data of structural loads were generated by simulating an array of three IEA 22MW turbines in the simulation tool FAST.Farm (Jonkman et al., 2017). In total, 7,200 FAST.Farm simulations were conducted, including 12 turbulent seeds. The processed 10-minute data were averaged over the 12 seeds to ensure statistical convergence, making it 600 cases. As each FAST.Farm simulation comprises three turbines, the location-agnostic surrogates are trained based on 1800 cases. The ambient wind speeds, the ambient turbulence intensity, the vertical shear, the wind direction, the inter-turbine spacings, the yaw misalignments, as well as the power demand of each turbine were varied across these training cases in order to create a large and rich dataset. In particular, the previous load surrogates in Guilloré et al. (2024) and Guilloré et al. (2025) had limited application range around the rated wind speeds of the turbine, as this is where wind farm control is most beneficial. But for a holistic application in the *Control Room of the Future*, the new surrogate for the IEA 22MW covers the whole operational wind speed range of the turbine (i.e., from 3 to 25 m/s). The load surrogates are trained using as inputs four sector-averaged wind speeds (SAWS) and four sector-averaged turbulence intensities (SATI) as in Guilloré et al. (2024). Detailed analysis in Guilloré et al. (2025) showed that this is a suitable choice to balance between complexity and accuracy. In contrast with Guilloré et al. (2024), the curtailment level is not characterized for the surrogate by the 10-minute mean blade pitch angle and 10-minute mean rotor speed, but rather by the percentage of power demand (100% being full rated power of the turbine). This is directly motivated by the application using reduced-order models, where it is easier to accurately know the prescribed power demand rather than the resulting blade pitch angle and rotor speed which are secondary consequences.

For the results illustrated here, the DELs projected along maximum damage di-

rection are used, following the method presented in Guilloré et al. (2024). That is, for each of the load locations listed below, and at each time step, two orthogonal components of a given load are projected along all possible directions, with an angular step of 10° . All corresponding DELs are computed and the maximum value is then stored as the "projected DEL." This projection is necessary to identify the most damaged direction on each cross section. The projected load channels considered here and their orthogonal components are:

- "**DEL Blade root**": blade root in-plane and out-of-plane bending moments.
- "**DEL Shaft**": shaft out-of-plane and yaw bending moments.
- "**DEL Tower top**": tower top fore-aft and side-side bending moments.
- "**DEL Tower base**": tower bottom fore-aft and side-side bending moments.

The full resulting distributions of local inflow parameters, control set-points, and main DELs are shown in Fig. 2.1, showing the large applicability range of the trained surrogates.

The load surrogates are trained using artificial neural networks following the approach in Guilloré et al. (2024), as the detailed analysis in Guilloré et al. (2025) proved it to be a viable architecture. After randomly shuffling, half of the 1800 cases are used for training, while the other half is used for testing. The resulting performances are shown in Table 2.1. The surrogates achieved acceptable accuracy, with RMSPE values below 10% across all channels for testing cases. This indicates readiness for application to case studies on the IEA 22 MW reference turbine.

Table 2.1: Root-mean-square percentage errors (RMSPE) of the new load surrogates for the IEA 22MW wind turbine.

	Power	DEL Blade root	DEL Shaft	DEL Tower top	DEL Tower base
Training RMSPE (%)	3.28	0.605	3.73	2.71	6.05
Testing RMSPE (%)	6.22	1.60	6.21	4.16	9.63

Figures 2.2 and 2.3 show examples of predictions of the trained load surrogates for varying wind farm control actions. These are meant to illustrate how the trained load surrogates are able to capture the effect of WFC actions on the structural loads of any turbine in a wind farm. For WT1, which is actuated, the local inflow remains unchanged, but the surrogates correctly map the variation of DELs based on the yaw misalignment (Fig. 2.2) and level of power demand (Fig. 2.3). For the downstream turbines WT2 and WT3, the surrogates are unaware of the changes of control actions in the first turbine WT1. The control setpoints of WT2 and WT3 are unchanged, but the surrogates correctly map the variations of DELs based on

Figure 2.1: Distribution of the sector-averaged wind speeds (SAWS), sector-averaged turbulence intensities (SATI), yaw misalignment and power demand used in the training of the new load surrogate model for the IEA 22MW reference turbines. It shows its large applicability range. In addition, the last rows displays the distributions of predicted outputs (damage equivalent loads at various locations).

the local inflow quantities that these rotors are experiencing. Figures 2.2 and 2.3 illustrate the possible effect of WFC on the power and fatigue loadings of three turbines in an array, showcasing the capabilities of the surrogates. It should be kept in mind that the DELs are very specific to the selected case of ambient wind speeds, turbulence intensities, wind direction and turbine locations. It is always hard to draw intuitive generic conclusions on the effect of WFC on the loadings of downstream turbines. Hence the high need of generic and accurate load surrogate models as

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are being developed in the SUDOCO project.

Figure 2.2: Exemplary predictions of the load surrogates (dashed lines, denoted ANN for Artificial Neural Network) against simulation values (solid lines) for the IEA 22MW turbine. The yaw misalignment of the upstream turbine WT1 (and thus its wake deflection) is varied along the X-axis. Data are shown for a staggered array of three IEA 22MW turbines as displayed in the center (wind direction $+4^\circ$). In this exemplary case, the ambient wind speed is 10m/s , turbulence intensity of 6%, vertical shear of 0.2, inter-turbine spacing of $6D$, and no curtailment control modes (100% power demand at each turbine).

These new load surrogate models for the IEA 22MW reference turbine are ready to be applied and they have been shared with all partners in the project's GitHub repository. They take the form of simple estimating functions that take as inputs the four sector-averaged wind speeds (SAWS, in m/s), four sector-averaged turbulence intensities (SATI, in $\%$), the yaw misalignment (in deg) and the power demand (in $\%$). For further details on these quantities, please refer to Guilloré et al. (2024) and Guilloré et al. (2025). The local inflow (SAWS + SATI) can be estimated by lower-order steady-state wake models such as FLORIS (Fleming et al., 2020) or PyWake (Pedersen et al., 2023).

The coupling of these state-of-the-art steady-state wake models and SUDOCO's new load surrogate models, allows for a computationally cheap estimation of fatigue loadings for the IEA 22MW turbine in any wind farm layout, any wind conditions, and any wind farm control actions. This can be used for optimisation of control settings to holistically maximise the power of wind farms while minimising the fatigue loadings at all turbine components of interest.

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Figure 2.3: Exemplary predictions of the load surrogates (dashed lines, denoted ANN for Artificial Neural Network) against simulation values (solid lines) for the IEA 22MW turbine. The power demand of the upstream turbine WT1 (and thus its wake strength) is varied along the X-axis. Data are shown for an aligned array of three IEA 22MW turbines as displayed in the center (wind direction 0°). In this exemplary case, the ambient wind speed is 12m/s, turbulence intensity of 6%, vertical shear of 0.2, inter-turbine spacing of 5D, and no yaw misalignment.

To combine the various short-term structural fatigue metrics (DELs and others) of various turbine components, SUDOCO T2.3 focuses on developing Health models. These tools allow a quantification of the effect of wind farm control actions on the structural integrity of any turbine in a farm integrated over a large period of time (lifetime). The details of the Health models are provided in the Deliverable D2.2 (Pettas et al., 2025). This work also contains more details on the coupling of the load surrogate model with steady-state wake models from Pedersen et al. (2023).

2.2 Coupling of the static models

This section details the integration of a novel wake model for wake mixing control, developed within WP1, into the *PyWake* simulation environment. The modifications allow for the simulation and optimization of wind farm control strategies that utilize dynamic induction control, specifically the “helix” approach, in combination with conventional wake steering. Furthermore, we will demonstrate the integration of these advanced flow models with the load surrogate models developed in WP2, enabling a

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holistic assessment of novel control strategies on both power production and turbine loading.

2.2.1 Modifications to the PyWake source code

To incorporate the helix control strategy, several modifications were made to the core components of the *PyWake* framework. These changes were designed to be modular, allowing for the new functionalities to be seamlessly integrated with existing models. The primary modifications were targeted at the wind turbine, wind farm, and wake deficit model objects.

The wind turbine object

The standard representation of a wind turbine in *PyWake* defines its power and thrust coefficient (C_P and C_T) as a function of the incoming wind speed. To account for the helix control, which involves periodic pitching of the blades, we have introduced a dependency of these curves on the helix amplitude. A custom *PowerCtFunction* was created, which takes both the wind speed and the helix amplitude as inputs.

The power and thrust penalties associated with the helix operation are modeled using third-order polynomial fits, which return a scalar value that is then multiplied by the baseline thrust and power curves:

$$P_{\text{loss}}(A_{\text{helix}}) = p_1 A_{\text{helix}}^3 + p_2 A_{\text{helix}}^2 + p_3 A_{\text{helix}} + p_4, \quad (2.1)$$

$$C_{T,\text{loss}}(A_{\text{helix}}) = q_1 A_{\text{helix}}^3 + q_2 A_{\text{helix}}^2 + q_3 A_{\text{helix}} + q_4. \quad (2.2)$$

Here, A is the helix amplitude, and p_i and q_i are the polynomial coefficients. This new functionality is encapsulated within the helix C_T loss function, which is then used to initialize a new *WindTurbine* object. This allows the wind farm model to query the power and thrust of each turbine based on its operational state, including its specific helix amplitude.

The wind farm object

The wind farm model is responsible for propagating the wakes downstream and calculating the effective wind speed at each turbine. We have extended the existing propagation models (*PropagateDownwind*, *PropagateUpDownIterative*, and *All2AllIterative*) to handle the helix control parameter. This was achieved by creating new classes, such as *PropagateDownwindHelix*, *PropagateUpDownIterativeHelix*, and *All2AllIterativeHelix*, which inherit from the base classes.

The main modification was the introduction of a new input parameter referring to the helix amplitude, to the *propagate deficit* method. This parameter is a multi-dimensional array that holds the helix amplitude for each turbine (i), wind direction (l), and wind speed (k):

$$\mathbf{H} = [h_{ilk}] \quad \forall i \in [1, N_{wt}], l \in [1, N_{wd}], k \in [1, N_{ws}] \quad (2.3)$$

Within the propagation loop, the helix amplitude for the current upstream turbine is passed as an argument to the wake deficit and turbulence models. This ensures that the wake characteristics are correctly calculated based on the turbine's operational mode. The code snippet below illustrates how the helix amplitude is extracted and passed to the model arguments.

```
...
helix_amp_mk = ilk2mk(kwargs.get('helix_amp_ilk', [[[0]]]))
...
arg_funcs = {...,
              'helix_amp_ilk': lambda: helix_amp_mk[m][na],
              ...}
model_kwargs = {k: arg_funcsk for k in self.args4all
                if k in arg_funcs}
...
```

The wake deficit model object

A new wake deficit model, *SuperGaussianHelixDeficit*, was developed to capture the enhanced wake recovery induced by the helix control. It is based on existing formulations, but has been extended to include the effect of the helix amplitude on the wake expansion and deficit.

In the *SuperGaussianHelixDeficit* model, the helix amplitude influences the parameters of the super-Gaussian function that describes the wake shape. Specifically, the wake width σ , and the super-Gaussian order n , are now functions of the helix amplitude. The relationships are defined by polynomial fits derived from high-fidelity simulation data from WP1. For instance, the wake width is calculated as:

$$\sigma_{ijklk} = (a_s(A_{ilk}) \cdot TI_{eff,ijklk} + b_s(A_{ilk})) \frac{x_{ijklk}}{D_i} + c_s(A_{ilk}) \sqrt{\beta_{ilk}}, \quad (2.4)$$

where a_s , b_s , and c_s are functions of the helix amplitude A_{ilk} , $TI_{eff,ijklk}$ is the effective turbulence intensity, x_{ijklk} is the downstream distance, D_i is the rotor diameter of the upstream turbine, and β_{ilk} is a function of the thrust coefficient which accesses the reduced thrust coefficient from the *WindTurbine* object.

2.2.2 Integration with load surrogate model

A key objective of SUDOCO is to enable a holistic optimisation of wind farm control, considering both energy yield and structural loading. To this end, the advanced wake models have been integrated with the load surrogate models developed in WP2. The load surrogates are data-driven models that predict damage equivalent loads on turbine components based on the local inflow conditions and control settings of the turbine.

The integration is achieved using the flow field calculated by our modified *PyWake* model as input to the load surrogates. For each turbine in the wind farm, the sector-averaged wind speeds and turbulence intensities are calculated. These values, along with the turbine's control settings (yaw misalignment and helix amplitude), are then fed into the load surrogate model to predict the resulting DELs:

$$DEL_{comp} = f_{surrogate}(SAWS, SATIs, \gamma, A_{helix}), \quad (2.5)$$

where γ is the yaw angle, and A_{helix} is the helix amplitude. More specifically, the load surrogate model that is used in this case is the Gaussian process load surrogate model developed by TU Delft in (Guilloré et al., 2025).

The coupling between the load surrogates and *PyWake* leverages the development of the `wind_farm_loads` package presented in Pettas et al. (2025), which extracts sector-averaged velocity and turbulence quantities from the rotor plane. During that work, we found it was essential to disregard the induction effects and added turbulence generated by each turbine within a surrounding sphere, as these otherwise interfere with the turbine measurements. This way, it is possible to compute physically meaningful wind speed and TI over each rotor. Further integrations between *PyWake*, the `wind_farm_loads` package and the helix control will be the object of future developments. To test this integration, we performed two-turbine simulations in which the crosswind direction of the second (downstream) turbine was varied in small increments as shown in Fig. 2.4. For each step, the load surrogate model embedded in the *PyWake* workflow produced predictions that were compiled into the loading plots. We then compared the load predictions from the surrogate model operating within the *PyWake* environment against its predictions when driven by data from high-fidelity aeroelastic simulations (i.e., OpenFAST with LES inflow).

Figures 2.5 and 2.6 compare the outputs of the load surrogate model given inputs from *PyWake* and large eddy simulations for different control cases. In the baseline case, the figures show a promising agreement between the two load surrogate inputs, demonstrating the viability of our integrated approach for load-aware wind farm control optimization. The blade root DELs in the case of helix control seem to be overestimated, primarily for small turbine spacing. This is mostly due to the current tuning procedure of the helix wake model, which is based on different large eddy simulations. Additional optimization of the helix wake model is required

Figure 2.4: Illustration of the simulations performed with *PyWake* to test the integration with the load surrogate model.

to improve the load prediction capabilities with *PyWake*. For wake steering, the load surrogate model with *PyWake* agrees well with the LES results.

2.2.3 Application: Integrated wind farm control optimization

The developed framework enables the optimization of wind farm control strategies that combine traditional wake steering with the novel helix control. We have implemented an exemplary sequential greedy optimization algorithm to determine the optimal yaw angles and helix amplitudes for each turbine in a wind farm to maximize the total power output. Figure 2.7 showcases the results of this optimization for a representative wind farm layout under a specific wind direction.

The ability to simulate and optimize these integrated control strategies, while also assessing their impact on structural loads, is a significant step towards the realization of the *Control Room of the Future*. This framework provides the necessary tools for operators to make informed decisions that balance the competing objectives of maximizing revenue and ensuring the long-term structural integrity of the wind farm assets.

2.3 Surrogate models coupled with dynamic models

The dynamic simulation framework used for the coupling with the load surrogate is OFF (Becker et al., 2025), an acronym derived from OnWARDS (Lejeune et al., 2022), FLORIDyn (Becker et al., 2022b), and FLORIS (Fleming et al., 2020). OFF has been developed as a unified, open-source toolbox designed to facilitate the comparison of different wake modeling approaches. Its key objectives are to: (i) design and implement interfaces with established steady-state model frameworks

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Figure 2.5: Validation of the integrated load surrogate model. The plots compare the blade root flapwise DELs predicted by the surrogate model using inputs from *PyWake* (red) versus inputs from aeroelastic simulations (black).

such as FLORIS and *PyWake*, (ii) provide a framework for prototyping dynamic wake models through standardized input–output structures, and (iii) offer accessibility via open-source Python code.

This versatility makes OFF an effective platform for benchmarking and experimentation. It enables comparisons between dynamic and steady-state wake models, while supporting the development of new Wind Farm Flow Control (WFFC)

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(a) Baseline

(b) Helix

(c) Wake steering

Figure 2.6: Validation of the integrated load surrogate model. The plots compare the tower base fore-aft DELs predicted by the surrogate model using inputs from *PyWake* (red) versus inputs from aeroelastic simulations (black).

strategies at low computational cost. Figure 2.8 illustrates the structure used in the current version of the code. The approach builds upon the *FLORIDyn* framework to capture state dynamics, such as wake advection, while employing *FLORIS* as the underlying steady-state wake model.

FLORIDyn itself is a parametric, control-oriented model intended for wind farm simulations. While *FLORIS* provides a steady-state approximation of the mean flow

Figure 2.7: Wind farm power optimization results for a single wind direction. The size of the turbine markers is proportional to their power output. In the optimized cases, the color of the markers indicates the control setting (yaw angle or helix amplitude).

field—neglecting temporal dynamics—FLORIDyn extends this concept by allowing the simulation of simplified wake dynamics over time. It can accommodate heterogeneous and transient flow conditions and captures the propagation of turbine state changes through the wake.

The OFF framework also makes use of the Turbine Wake Field (TWF) concept to approximate local ambient and wake conditions at a given turbine location. The TWF maps the dynamic state to a steady-state wake model (here FLORIS) for evaluation. Figure 5.3 illustrates this for a three-turbine example. Turbines T1 and T2 operate in free-stream conditions, while T3 is influenced by their wakes. T1 and T2 receive

Figure 2.8: Nested software architecture used for the results presented by Becker et al. (2022a): “The FLORIDyn framework is used to model the state dynamics, like the wake advection. The framework approximates the flow field at the location of each turbine and uses FLORIS to calculate measurements like effective wind speeds and power generated.”

Figure 2.9: OP propagation for a three-turbine example (Becker et al., 2025)

wind field input, add their states, and generate an operating point (OP). This OP then propagates downstream, and for each impacting wake, one OP is interpolated from the two closest OPs. Its state is obtained through distance-based interpolation, thereby approximating the environment of T3. The resulting TWF is passed to the surrogate steady-state model, which then returns predictions such as effective wind speed and generated power.

In practice, the dynamic inflow conditions predicted by OFF—such as effective wind speeds, turbulence intensities, and wake-induced flow transients—are averaged over time and passed to the load surrogate. The surrogate then maps these conditions to turbine load responses. In this way, OFF provides the dynamic flow environment, while the surrogate translates the resulting flow field into structural loading predictions. This coupling allows the evaluation of control strategies in terms of both power production and structural response, at a fraction of the computational cost of full CFD or high-fidelity aeroelastic simulations.

However, in the context of the SUDOCO project, the load surrogates have been designed to align with state-of-the-art static models in the wind industry. A recurring challenge in this process is matching the inflow conditions of the higher-order models and lower-order surrogates. While the surrogates are trained using aeroelastic

simulations, which provide the data required for load calculations, the lower-order models themselves are primarily designed for accurate power prediction. This mismatch introduces discrepancies that will have to be investigated and addressed. In the Demonstrations of the *Control Room of the Future* (D6.2), a demonstration of the dynamic coupling will be presented in the context of control rooms of the future.

2.4 Surrogate model adaptation for floating wind turbines

To enable the *Control Room of the Future* also for floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs), more advanced surrogate models—compared to those developed for bottom-fixed turbines—are required. This is due to the following reasons:

- FOWTs exhibit strong coupling between the aerodynamic loads on the rotor, the hydrodynamic loads on the platform, and the servo-elastic response of the entire structure. This intricate coupling is far more pronounced than in bottom-fixed turbines and means that a change in wind inflow not only affects the turbine but also excites the platform, which in turn influences the aerodynamic loads. The surrogate model must be able to capture these complex, two-way interactions.
- FOWTs possess additional degrees of freedom (DOF), such as platform surge, heave, and pitch, which make the modeling of the rotor inflow more complex. Even though the platform motion is typically restrained by a mooring line system, certain mooring types, e.g., catenary moorings, may allow motions on the order of 10 m, which may add a considerable offset of the rotor towards the incoming wake of an upstream turbine. In addition, a changed nacelle yaw angle also changes the direction of the turbines thrust, causing an offset of the platform.
- FOWTs are build up of additional components compared to bottom-fixed turbines. These require additional load channels to be considered in the damage predictions. In particular, the mooring line fatigue loads have been found to be of critical importance. A parametric pre-study of the dependence of mooring line fatigue on varying inflow conditions in deliverable D2.1 (Guilloré et al., 2025) found that variations in inflow turbulence may strongly impact the fatigue loads—and thus the lifetime—of the mooring line system.
- Additional environmental inputs are required. These are typically the sea states, such as wave height time series or wave spectra with wave heights and periods and the water current.
- The wind turbine controller for a floating system has a dual objective: optimizing power capture and ensuring platform stability. Control actions, like blade

pitch adjustments, have a significant effect on platform motion and can directly influence fatigue on components like the tower base and mooring lines. This control-induced dynamic behavior is a critical input that the surrogate model must account for.

- The inclusion of sea states and platform dynamics drastically expands the parameter space. This necessitates the generation of a much larger and more computationally expensive set of training data from fully coupled aero-hydro-servo-elastic simulations to ensure the surrogate model is robust and accurate across all operational conditions.

At this point, no surrogate model for an FOWT has been developed within the project. Nevertheless, the integration of a future surrogate model into the *Control Room of the Future* can be relatively straightforward. That is, the complexity lies within the surrogate model itself and its development. Most importantly for the integration into the *Control Room of the Future*, the sea state for a given wind condition needs to be provided or estimated. This environmental input is essential, as the hydrodynamic loads from waves are a dominant factor in the fatigue and ultimate loads experienced by FOWT components, particularly the mooring system and tower base. In contrast, the specifics of the controller, adapted for floating, should already be incorporated in the surrogate model.

2.5 Structural health monitoring for floating wind turbines

Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) for FOWTs is an important component of the *Control Room of the Future*. As previously established, the control room will enable operators to manage the wind farm with diverse, real-time objectives, such as optimizing revenue or minimizing structural damage. To support such objective-driven management, a comprehensive, high-resolution understanding of the wind farm's structural condition is essential, making SHM an indispensable tool for FOWT operations.

While monitoring solutions for bottom-fixed offshore wind turbines are widely available, the installation method of the moored floating system used in the floating offshore wind industry presents unique and significant challenges. For decades, the offshore oil and gas industry has used direct sensing methods, using subsea sensors to monitor mooring systems and floater structures. However, this approach is economically unfeasible for the highly cost-sensitive floating wind industry due to the high costs and maintenance efforts associated with subsea sensors in the harsh offshore environment. Therefore, a new, more economical approach is essential for the widespread adoption of floating wind technology.

Within the SUDOCO project, the D2.3 deliverable "Monitoring Strategies for Floating Wind Turbines" (Jacob et al., 2025) provides a comprehensive review of

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the challenges, requirements, and state of the art in FOWT monitoring. The most promising and cost-effective solution is the use of digital twins that leverage virtual sensing (Cevasco et al., 2022). This approach enables unmeasured signals, such as mooring line tension and fatigue loads, to be inferred using a model of the FOWT and the sensor data typically available from the FOWT, such as its position and orientation. In particular, the D2.3 report highlights that physics-based digital twins, like those based on a Kalman filter, are highly suitable for this task. Unlike purely data-driven models that require huge amounts of training data, physics-based models are more flexible and adaptable. They can be easily adjusted to account for changes in the FOWT's system behavior over its lifetime, such as degradation or marine growth. This ability to retune the model is crucial, as a sensitivity study within D2.3 confirms that even small changes in parameters like mooring length or diameter can lead to significant errors in virtual sensed signals, especially in fatigue load estimations. This highlights the need for a digital twin model to be able to adapt efficiently, which physics-based approaches excel at.

Therefore, the SUDOCO project is developing a physics-based digital twin using the SLOW (Streamlined Advanced and Low-Fidelity Floating Wind simulation) model (Lemmer, 2018) to build a Kalman filter. This digital twin will act as a foundational upstream module within the framework of the *Control Room of the Future*. It will not be directly involved in the real-time control loops, but rather provide the farm operator with the necessary insights into the structural health and condition of the floating wind farm. This essential data empowers the operator to make informed decisions about farm management, such as risk-based inspections and deciding whether to optimize for maximum power output or to reduce fatigue on a particular turbine to extend its lifespan, ensuring both economic viability and structural integrity over the entire operational lifetime of the farm.

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3 Economic Value Functions

A central objective of the SUDOCO project is to optimise the economic value of future offshore wind farms through the co-design of the wind farm layout and control. To this end, this chapter defines the net present value as an economic performance indicator and introduces a mathematical model of the operations and maintenance costs. The cost model captures the financial impact of changes in wind farm control, allowing for the economic optimization of wind farm control strategies.

3.1 Economic value of wind energy

To optimise wind farm control in volatile markets, the *Control Room of the Future* requires an economic objective function that incorporates price volatility. We use the net present value (NPV), which represents the income of the investment throughout its lifetime, discounted to today's value:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{NPV} &= \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{I_t}{(1+r)^t} \\ &= \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{R_t - C_t}{(1+r)^t} \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

where:

- I_t : Net cash inflow or income in year t
- N : Expected life of the investment (in years)
- t : Year of operation
- r : Discount rate
- C_t : Total expenditure in year t
- R_t : Revenue in year t

The NPV metric represents the financial balance between the costs and revenue. Another often-used financial performance metric is the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE), which represents the balance between the cost and energy yield. The

LCOE includes the same cost components as the NPV, except it ignores the price volatility. Since price volatility is a crucial aspect of the future wind energy market, the *Control Room of the Future* will focus on the NPV as the primary economic objective function.

To investigate how the general expression of NPV (Equation 3.1) applies to wind energy projects, we define the NPV for a wind farm:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{NPV} &= \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{R_t - C_t}{(1+r)^t} \\
 &= \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{\bar{p}_t \cdot \eta_t^{O\&M} \cdot \text{AEV}_t - (C_t^{O\&M} + C_t^{\text{CAPEX}})}{(1+r)^t} \\
 &= \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{\bar{p}_t \cdot \frac{N^h - T_t^{O\&M}}{N^h} \cdot \text{AEV}_t - (C_t^{O\&M} + C_t^{\text{CAPEX}})}{(1+r)^t}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

where:

- \bar{p}_t : Mean market price of electricity (revenue per unit of energy) in year t
- $\eta_t^{O\&M}$: Availability due to operations and maintenance in year t
- AEV_t : Net annual energy value produced in year t , including wake losses
- $N^h = 8766$: Number of hours in a year
- $T_t^{O\&M}$: Operations and maintenance downtime (in hours) in year t
- $C_t^{O\&M}$: Operations and maintenance cost in year t
- C_t^{CAPEX} : Capital expenditures (CAPEX) in year t

Equation 3.2 writes the wind farm revenue as the product of the mean electricity price, the operations and maintenance (O&M) availability factor, and the net annual energy value (AEV) (Bechmann et al., 2024). The availability factor explicitly accounts for the losses due to O&M downtime, while the net AEV implicitly includes price volatility and wake losses. By separating O&M downtime from energy value estimation, we neglect the small effect that downtime has on wake losses. When a wind turbine undergoes repairs, it does not generate a wake; however, the chosen formulation greatly simplifies NPV computations.

To apply the NPV as a control objective for future wind farms, we identify every element in Equation 3.2 that depends on wind farm control and develop numerical models for each. Wind turbine control and inflow are directly connected; we must therefore include both:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{\bar{P}_t \cdot \frac{N^h - T_t^{O\&M} [f(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{c})]}{N^h} \cdot AEV_t [f(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{c})] - (C_t^{O\&M} [f(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{c})] + C_t^{CAPEX})}{(1+r)^t} \quad (3.3)$$

where:

- $\mathbf{u} = [u, TI, \dots]$: Vector of inflow variables, such as wind speed and turbulence intensity
- $\mathbf{c} = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n]$: Vector of control variables, such as yaw angle, cut-out speed, and de-rating
- $f(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{c})$: Probability density function (PDF) of inflow conditions and control settings

Three parts of the NPV depend on the wind turbine control variables: The yearly O&M costs ($C_t^{O\&M}$), O&M downtime ($T_t^{O\&M}$), and AEV production (AEV_t). Modelling of the O&M costs is described in Section 3.2, while Bechmann and Quick (2025) describe an AEV model that incorporates price volatility by introducing a correlation between electricity prices and wind speeds.

3.2 Operations and maintenance costs

Wind turbines are subject to repetitive loads that can cause degradation and potentially lead to component failure if not regularly maintained. The rate of damage accumulation of an operating turbine depends on the turbine design, the turbine control, and its inflow. The O&M model hypothesises that a significant part of wind turbine O&M costs is due to component degradation requiring unplanned maintenance. The remaining part is a yearly scheduled cost that scales with the turbine's CAPEX. The unplanned maintenance cost is distributed across several turbine components and scaled up or down according to estimated damage rates.

There are many ways to categorise and model O&M events of wind turbines (Malik and Bak, 2024; Loepelmann and Fischer, 2022; Réthoré et al., 2014). Due to the significant uncertainty and complexity of modelling the O&M process, we define just two categories: fixed costs for regular operations, and variable costs for unplanned maintenance:

- Operations: Cost for scheduled servicing, administration, and insurance, independent of the wind turbine control strategy
- Maintenance: Cost due to component degradation that requires unplanned repairs or replacements, e.g. gearbox, generator, bearings, leading edges of blades, etc.

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Using the two O&M categories and the model assumptions, we write the yearly O&M costs (Equation 3.3) as:

$$\begin{aligned} C_t^{O\&M} &= C_t^O + \sum_{i=1}^{N^c} C_{it}^M [D_{it}, C] \\ T_t^{O\&M} &= T_t^O + \sum_{i=1}^{N^c} T_{it}^M [D_{it}] \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

where:

- T_t^O & C_t^O : Operations costs, in hours and euros respectively, in year t
- T_{it}^M & C_{it}^M : Maintenance costs, in hours and euros respectively, in year t for component i
- N^c : Number of components being tracked for degradation damage

As seen, the yearly O&M costs consist of a constant planned part and an unplanned part that increases yearly as component damage accumulates.

The number of components tracked for degradation damage (N^c) depends on the application of the O&M model. Some operational conditions of a wind turbine may cause an increased damage rate for some components and a decreased rate for others. It is necessary to include enough components to capture the correct trends of the O&M costs. On the other hand, each component needs a load model (load surrogate). Too many components might necessitate an oversimplification of these load models. Nine components are used in this report (main bearing, blades, pitch bearing, gearbox, main shaft, yaw bearing, tower, generator, power converter). Still, other applications may use different numbers - the turbine could even be represented as a single component.

3.2.1 Operations costs

While the maintenance costs (C_t^M and T_t^M) are the most interesting from a control optimisation viewpoint, the regular operations costs (C_t^O and T_t^O) must also be realistic.

As the overall goal of the cost model is to capture the financial impact of a change in wind farm control, we define a reference situation where the wind turbine operates under standard control and inflow conditions. The costs under reference conditions are set to values found in the literature for offshore wind turbines (Szabó, 2025). If the wind farm control changes, the operations costs (C_t^O and T_t^O) are kept fixed at the reference level, while the maintenance costs (C_t^M and T_t^M) are recalculated for the new conditions. We suggest the following operations costs:

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$$\begin{aligned} C_t^O &= C_t^{O,ref} = 3.2\% \cdot C - \bar{C}^{M,ref} \\ T_t^O &= T_t^{O,ref} = 3.0\% \cdot N^h - \bar{T}^{M,ref} \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

where:

- $\bar{T}^{M,ref}$ & $\bar{C}^{M,ref}$: Lifetime mean unplanned maintenance costs under reference conditions

where superscript *ref* is used to indicate that a variable is evaluated under reference inflow and control conditions. To estimate the operations costs, it is necessary first to calculate the unplanned maintenance costs under reference conditions; this is the subject of the next section.

3.2.2 Maintenance costs

The unplanned maintenance cost is modelled as the product of a component's replacement costs and its probability of failure:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{it}^M [D_{it}, C] &= \lambda_{it} [D_{it}] \cdot C_i^{replace} [C] \\ T_{it}^M [D_{it}] &= \lambda_{it} [D_{it}] \cdot T_i^{replace} \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

where:

- $C_i^{replace}$: Cost needed to replace component *i*
- $T_i^{replace}$: Time needed to replace component *i*
- λ_{it} : Probability of failure of component *i* during year *t* given survival through year *t-1*

As we require a computationally efficient model suitable for control optimisation, we model the probability of failure while applying fixed replacement costs for each component. The model for unplanned maintenance uses the probability of failure of a component to distribute its replacement cost over the turbine's lifetime. While a real-life component fails at a specific time, the unplanned maintenance model distributes its replacement cost over time. This is done to reflect the uncertainty in actual failure timing and supports long-term planning of maintenance budgets.

Component replacement costs

The unplanned maintenance cost is estimated using pre-defined replacement costs and downtime hours for each wind turbine component (Equation 3.6). This is an approximation, as actual wind turbine repair costs depend on the costs of the repair staff, transport costs, vessel availability, weather windows, etc. However, the use of pre-defined replacement costs that include all these sub-costs makes the O&M model computationally fast and transparent. Examples of how replacement costs and downtime hours can be estimated using high-fidelity simulations of each repair event are provided by Donnelly et al. (2024).

Component failure modelling

The probability of a component failure as a function of accumulated degradation damage is modelled using the Weibull cumulative distribution function F :

$$\lambda_{it} [D_{it}] = F_{it} - F_{it-1} \quad (3.7)$$

$$F_{it} = 1 - \exp\left(- (D_{it})^{k_i}\right)$$

where:

- F_{it} : Probability of failure up till year t for component i
- k_i : Weibull shape parameter for component i

3.2.3 Component degradation modelling

Assuming a constant yearly damage accumulation rate, the component degradation damage is given by:

$$D_{it} \approx t \cdot \frac{\partial D_i}{\partial t} \quad (3.8)$$

$$\approx \frac{t}{t_i^{ref}} \cdot \left(\frac{\bar{L}_i}{\bar{L}_i^{ref}}\right)^{m_i}$$

where:

- t_i^{ref} : Reference life of component i in years. Determined from empirical data
- \bar{L}_i : Lifetime damage-equivalent load (DEL) for component i

- \bar{L}_i^{ref} : Lifetime DEL for component i under reference conditions
- m_i : Wöhler exponent of component i

Equation 3.8 assumes a known reference life for each wind turbine component and applies a relative change in their DEL (damage-equivalent load) when going from reference to new operating conditions to determine the new component life. We must determine the component reference life from empirical data on failure rates or use the component's design rating life. We estimate the expected lifetime DEL under inflow conditions (\mathbf{u}) and control strategy (\mathbf{c}) using a load surrogate:

$$\bar{L}_i^{m_i} = \int_0^\infty L_i(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{c})^{m_i} f(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{c}) d\mathbf{u} d\mathbf{c} \quad (3.9)$$

where:

- $L_i(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{c})$: The damage-equivalent load (DEL) amplitude for component i under inflow conditions \mathbf{u} and control settings \mathbf{c}

The inflow and control conditions used to estimate a component's reference DEL (\bar{L}_i^{ref}) and the inflow and control conditions used to estimate its characteristic life (t_i^{ref}) are assumed to be the same.

4 Environmental Value Functions

A major focus of the SUDOCO project is the determination and maximisation of the environmental value through optimisation of future offshore wind farm designs and control strategies. Several performance indicators have been defined in the SUDOCO context, and corresponding calculation methods have been developed. In the following, these methods are shortly introduced. For more details and demonstrating results, the reader is referred to the cited deliverables and scientific papers.

4.1 Environmental cost of wind energy

The first relevant metric is the environmental cost of energy (COE_{CO_2}) linked to climate change impact, also termed carbon footprint. COE_{CO_2} reflects all direct and indirect greenhouse gas emissions generated due to infrastructure and logistics throughout the life cycle of a wind farm, termed Total Life Cycle Emissions ($TLCE$), and relates them to the Total lifetime Energy Production (TEP) of the farm:

$$COE_{CO_2} = \frac{TLCE}{TEP}. \quad (4.1)$$

To enable the calculation of COE_{CO_2} linked to offshore wind energy, the Design and Evaluation Toolchain with Eco-Conscious Targets (DETECT) has been developed through the SUDOCO project. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is applied to calculate the greenhouse gas emissions linked to each life phase of a wind farm from-cradle-to-grave. The emissions of each life phase sum up to the plant's $TLCE$. Wind farm simulation software is used to calculate the annual energy production (AEP) of a farm, considering wake and other losses and involving the possibility of applying different wind farm control strategies. DETECT enables the automated quantification of the carbon footprint associated with typical European offshore wind farm designs. The toolchain has been presented in detail in Kainz et al. (2024a) and Kainz et al. (2024b).

DETECT captures the impact of wind farm control on the carbon footprint of offshore wind farms through the associated energy production and the plant lifetime. Furthermore, the emissions linked to the O&M phase are calculated based on the failure rates of the individual offshore wind turbine components. If changes in the failure rates through wind farm control activities are captured, DETECT can process this information and translate it into the associated changes in carbon footprint.

However, the O&M formulation in DETECT is statistics-based and aims at the determination of typical O&M-related life-cycle emissions. To assess time-series of O&M emissions linked to specific O&M strategies, a recent SUDOCO effort has augmented the “Windfarm Operations and Maintenance cost-Benefit Analysis Tool” (WOMBAT), developed by NREL (Hammond and Cooperman, 2022), with a detailed emission assessment. Based on the individual component failure rates and weather time-series, the detailed vessel activities required for the operation and maintenance of an offshore wind farm are calculated. The data is then post-processed to calculate the emissions linked to (a) the fuel emissions linked to vessel operation, (b) the life-cycle emissions linked to the vessels themselves, and (c) the emissions linked to spare parts required for replacement activities. A sensitivity analysis has been performed to understand the impact of the failure rates on the associated O&M emissions and costs. The results have been presented in the EERA DeepWind Conference 2025, the associated conference paper (Gräfe et al., 2025) has been accepted for publication. The preprint of the paper can be found in Appendix A, details about the method and the results of the sensitivity analysis can be found there.

4.2 Environmental value of energy

The next metric is the environmental value of energy (VOE_{CO_2}) related to the operation of a wind farm. The metric reflects the greenhouse gas emissions displaced in the electricity grid that the farm is connected to. In today’s dynamic and interconnected energy systems, wind energy often displaces other – primarily fossil fuel-based – power plants. The corresponding displaced grid greenhouse gas emissions GHG_{disp} related to the displacing wind energy fed into the grid E_{disp} define the environmental value of wind energy VOE_{CO_2} at a time instance t :

$$VOE_{CO_2}(t) = \frac{GHG_{disp}(t)}{E_{disp}(t)} \quad (4.2)$$

The instantaneous environmental value of energy depends on the operational state of the system and is thereby strongly time-dependent. To assess the value of energy over a period of time, $VOE_{CO_2}(t)$ is integrated over that period. The lifetime environmental value of energy $VOE_{CO_2,tot}$ is determined by integration over the farm lifetime. Typically $VOE_{CO_2,tot}$ is multiple times larger than COE_{CO_2} , highlighting the crucial role of wind energy in the energy transition towards climate-friendly energy systems.

To determine $VOE_{CO_2}(t)$, the potential of a wind farm to displace emissions in the connected grid has to be assessed first. This potential is defined as the Marginal Displacement Factor of wind MDF_{wind} , expressed in kilograms of car-

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bon dioxide equivalent per megawatt-hour produced ($\text{kgCO}_2\text{e/MWh}$). MDF_{wind} captures changes in grid emissions resulting from incremental variations in wind energy generation, while accounting for the time-dependent fluctuations in grid emissions driven by the generation mix and demand-supply dynamics. MDF_{wind} is an energy system metric and independent of the location of a wind farm within the regarded system. As generation mix and demand-supply dynamics are highly time-varying, MDF_{wind} is a time-series metric. The SUDOCO method to calculate MDF_{wind} can be applied on any control zone, market region or country as long as time-series of generation mix, imports and exports as well as the associated emission factors are available. Once determined, the (time-series of) MDF_{wind} is multiplied with the (time-series of) energy production $E_{wind}(t)$ of a wind farm and its potential change through wind farm control to determine the associated VOE_{CO_2} :

$$VOE_{CO_2}(t) = MDF_{wind}(t) \cdot E_{wind}(t) \quad (4.3)$$

The definition of MDF and the calculation method have first been proposed in Kainz et al. (2024b), and then been further developed and presented at the EERA DeepWind Conference 2025 (Kainz et al., 2025b; Kainz et al., 2025a). Compared to the initial version, a grid balance constraint has been applied to the definition of the MDF that ensures that changes in demand are always met by supply and vice versa. The conference paper presenting and demonstrating the advanced MDF formulation has been accepted for publication. The preprint of the article is attached to this Deliverable in Appendix B, details about the method can be found there.

4.3 Environmental net value of energy

Finally, the environmental net value of energy ($NVOE_{CO_2}$) reflects the emissions avoided in the connected electricity system throughout the lifetime of the regarded wind farm. It is determined by subtracting the environmental cost of energy from the lifetime environmental value of energy:

$$NVOE_{CO_2} = VOE_{CO_2,tot} - COE_{CO_2} \quad (4.4)$$

The $NVOE_{CO_2}$ takes into account both burden and benefit related to climate-change impact of offshore wind farms. This enables the holistic assessment of the environmental performance of offshore wind farms.

The automated setup of the described tools and methods enables design and control strategy optimisation to minimise or maximise the presented environmental performance indicators. These objective functions are an integral part of SUDOCO's *Control Room of the Future* and will be subject to wind farm control optimisation and co-design applications during the SUDOCO project and beyond, next to considerations about energy yield, fatigue loads, reliability, and economic revenue.

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5 Control Strategies of the Future

Combining various models and techniques into a single framework presents its own challenges, especially in terms of user-friendliness. The following strategies demonstrate different approaches to integrate their respective set of models: Lifetime-aware wind farm control, and the desirability approach.

5.1 The economic lifetime-aware wind farm control

The proposed economic lifetime-aware wind farm control formulation is designed to optimize wind farm operations over its entire lifetime. This section provides a brief overview of the proposed methodology. A publication manuscript that discusses details of the methodology and results obtained using relevant case studies is currently under review at the Wind Energy Science Journal (Anand et al., 2025).

Fatigue damage in a turbine component accumulates in a complex way over its lifespan, influenced by all ambient conditions encountered. Consequently, the damage accumulated under various wind conditions directly affects the remaining operational life of the turbine. As a result, a lifetime fatigue-aware wind farm controller must be optimised holistically, taking into account the entire spectrum of ambient conditions throughout the lifetime of the turbines.

Additionally, fatigue damage can significantly impact both the failure rate and the frequency of maintenance activities (Wilkinson et al., 2010; Scheu et al., 2017). This not only increases maintenance costs but also leads to economic losses because of the reduced power production during repair and maintenance periods.

The consideration of lifetime effects is integrated into the optimisation problem in two ways. First, the proposed optimisation ensures that the turbines operate for a specified duration without exceeding a predefined fatigue damage threshold. This threshold may represent the design lifetime of the turbine or a desired fraction of the remaining useful life, depending on the goals of the wind farm operator. This step is crucial, as failure to meet the threshold would result in revenue losses due to the reduced turbine lifespan. The second aspect of the proposed optimization focuses on maximizing the overall economic profit by accounting for the impact of fatigue damage on operation and maintenance costs. This is achieved by finding a trade-off between control actions aimed at increasing the economic value of power yield and those designed to mitigate the economic cost of fatigue damage.

The resulting optimisation provides an optimal schedule of setpoints for each turbine, tailored to the site's ambient wind conditions. This control formulation is

implemented in an open-loop fashion, similarly to widely used wake-control-based power-capture optimization strategies (Campagnolo et al., 2020; Göçmen et al., 2022; Howland et al., 2019), enabling the offline application of computationally intensive one-shot optimisations through steady-state simulations.

5.1.1 Optimisation problem

The optimisation problem can be written as

$$\max_{\mathbf{u}} \sum_T \text{Revenue}(\mathbf{W}_a, \mathbf{u}) - \text{Cost}(\mathbf{W}_a, \mathbf{u}), \quad (5.1a)$$

subject to

$$D_i^c(\mathbf{W}_a, \mathbf{u}) \leq D_{\text{ref}}^c \quad \forall i \in N \text{ and } \forall c \in C, \quad (5.1b)$$

and

$$\mathbf{u}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{u} \leq \mathbf{u}^{\max}. \quad (5.1c)$$

For a given set of ambient wind conditions \mathbf{W}_a , control set-points $\mathbf{u} = [\mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_i, \dots, \mathbf{u}_N]$ for N turbines in the farm, and C components in each turbine, the optimisation balances the accrued economic value through power generation $\text{Revenue}(\cdot)$ and the incurred economic cost due to maintenance activities and lost lifetime $\text{Cost}(\cdot)$, over a chosen lifetime T . The vector \mathbf{W}_a denotes the set of all wind conditions through time series of wind speeds, wind directions, and possibly other atmospheric parameters (turbulence intensity, shear), that occur over the lifetime T . In the present work, the considered ambient conditions are the hub height wind speed U , wind direction Γ , and turbulence intensity (TI) denoted as I , resulting in $\mathbf{W}_a = [U, \Gamma, I]$. Assuming the wind climate does not show any inter-annual variability, the time series can be approximated through a corresponding frequency distribution. Depending on the chosen WFC technique, the control set-point vector \mathbf{u}_i can consist of an induction factor α_i for induction control, yaw-offset γ_i for wake-steering, or a combination of the two.

The optimization problem is subjected to the lifetime constraint expressed by Eq. (5.1b), which ensures that the resulting lifetime damage D does not exceed the damage threshold D_{ref} . This parameter is an appropriate damage limit, which includes the necessary safety factors. Clearly, there are several options for determining the limit. For instance, D_{ref} could be set to the design limit, allowing the component to be utilized up to its maximum designed capacity. Alternatively, one might leave a damage margin, ensuring that the component has a second life and extending its overall usage. Despite the various possible scenarios, the underlying concept of this approach is to maintain control over damage accumulation while pursuing a specific goal. Achieving this goal would not be possible without an explicit

constraint to guide the process. In this work, for a given component c , D_{ref}^c is chosen as

$$D_{ref}^c = \max_i \sum_T D_i^c(\mathbf{W}_a) \quad \forall i \in N, \quad (5.2)$$

which corresponds to the maximum accumulated damage over all the turbines under the standard greedy control strategy, where no wake steering or other WFC strategies are applied. Furthermore, the optimisation problem is subjected to the bound constraint Eq. (5.1c) on the decision variable \mathbf{u} , where \mathbf{u}^{\min} and \mathbf{u}^{\max} denote the lower and upper bounds, respectively.

5.1.2 Optimisation framework

This section describes the optimisation framework designed to compute the optimal control setpoints for a wind farm using the proposed economic lifetime-aware WFC strategy. An overview of this framework, including its underlying models, is depicted in Fig. 5.1. The framework takes site-specific wind conditions \mathbf{W}_a as input and generates optimal control schedules $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{W}_a)$ for all turbines in the form of look-up tables.

Figure 5.1: Optimisation framework for the economic lifetime-aware formulation.

The equations in the grey-shaded region at the top of Fig. 5.1 highlight two key aspects of the proposed strategy: (i) the use of an economic merit function (Eq. 5.1a), and (ii) the lifetime constraint (Eq. 5.1b). Additionally, bounds on the control variables are enforced (Eq. 5.1c).

The underlying model set is represented by boxes with different color outlines in Fig. 5.1. The model toolchain consists of several components: a wind farm flow model, a fatigue load surrogate model, a damage estimation model, and an economic model.

The upper branch of the toolchain follows established research and industry practices for estimating the power production of the wind farm (Lee and Fields, 2020), which is then converted into economic revenue by the economic model. The lower branch tackles the more complex task of estimating the impact of the operational strategy on turbine components.

In this process, rotor inflow conditions are translated into DELs, which are then aggregated to estimate the damage to each specific component. The accumulated damage serves two purposes. First, the lifetime constraint evaluates whether the component damage is within the chosen threshold. Second, the economic model uses the accumulated damage to calculate the associated maintenance costs.

By combining the upper branch (revenue) and the lower branch (costs), the framework generates the economic profit metric, which is the objective of the optimisation.

5.2 The desirability approach

As wind energy matures as a staple of the modern-day electrical landscape, the tools to evaluate and quantify wind energy performance are increasing in complexity, enabling operators to make well-informed decisions, the complexity hinders holistic control decisions. Most works in wind farm flow control reduce multi-objective problems to a single economic objective or impose load-related constraints as safety checks (Liew et al., 2024b; Zhang et al., 2024). In contrast, the desirability approach presents a holistic evaluation strategy that values each objective according to its desirability in the operator's eyes, ensuring that these other disciplines are treated as objectives, not merely as constraints to the dominant economic objective.

This section presents a framework for wind farm flow control that enables the joint optimization of multiple operator-relevant objectives through desirability functions. These functions support a synchronous multi-objective optimization, based on the desirability of each objective from the operator's perspective.

5.2.1 Integrated Modelling Framework

To provide traceability of the computational steps, this section starts with an overview of the integrated models. At the core of the control strategy is the wind farm control technique, specifically wake steering, as described in Section 1.1. Wake steering is modelled using a combination of industry-standard approaches consisting of a wake model (Bastankhah and Porté-Agel, 2014), a wake deflection model (Jiménez et al., 2010), and a wake-added turbulence model (Frandsen, 2007). PyWake (Pedersen et al., 2023) is employed to compute the wind farm flow conditions for the different flow cases. These models are chosen for their trade-off between computational efficiency and accuracy.

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Figure 5.2: Flow chart of the wind farm controller design, utilising the desirability approach to calculate the structural objective function.

Additionally, to compute the loading parameters, the load surrogate described in Section 2.1 is used. The load channels available, including the blade root in-plane (BRIP), the blade root out-of-plane (BRPOP), the tower base side-to-side (TBSS), and the tower base fore-aft (TBFA), are the primary load channels for the load objective. The total optimization process is shown in the diagram of figure 5.2.

5.2.2 The desirability functions

The DELs form the basis to estimate cumulative turbine damage according to Hayman (2012), which is then translated into piecewise continuous desirability variables scaling from 0 to 1 (Derringer and Suich, 1980):

$$d(D) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } D > U \\ \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{U-D}{U-D^{BC}} \right]^s, & \text{if } U \geq D > D^{BC} \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(\left[\frac{D-D^{BC}}{D^{BC}-L} \right]^t + 1 \right), & \text{if } D^{BC} \geq D > L \\ 1, & \text{if } D < L \end{cases} \quad (5.3)$$

where the upper (U) limits are set as 105% of the base case damage, resulting in a range from base case damage to 105% base case damage. For the lower half of the desirability function, the range is from the lower limit (L), zero loading, to

Figure 5.3: Piecewise desirability function used to translate damage equivalent loads (DELs) into a normalized scale between 0 (undesirable) and 1 (desirable), with asymmetry between penalization of increased damage and reward for reduced damage relative to the base case.

base case loading. Parameters s and t are used to tune the slope of the piecewise functions. Both are set to 1. With the presented scaling, an increase in damage with respect to the Base Case (BC), without active wind farm control techniques, reduces desirability 20 times as effectively as a reduction in damage with respect to BC increases desirability. The desirability function is visualized in Figure ??.

All desirability variables are combined as a geometric mean to compute the load objective of each turbine (Derringer and Suich, 1980):

$$y_{n,Load} = (d(D_{BR}(x_n)) \times d(D_{YR}(x_n)) \times d(D_S(x_n)) \times d(D_{TB}(x_n)))^{1/4}. \quad (5.4)$$

5.2.3 Tuning of the desirability approach

To empower the operator with sufficient flexibility for most future cases, the desirability approach has several tweakable parameters to support such efforts. During the development process, several methods were conceived. This section describes the purpose and the implementation of these methods within the framework.

The tuning process has been primarily focused on optimising the desirability function approach for the load objective. Although the tuning functions operate similarly for other objectives, the naming and application are defined and tuned to the load channels. The three tuning options are 'Recalibrating target lifetime', 'Prioritize other objective', and 'Reduce/increase damage'. The tuning process of the desirability approach is shown in Figure 5.4.

The calibration of the desirability approach is an ongoing process that will be further optimised within Work Package 4.2.

Figure 5.4: Tuning process for the wind farm loads redistribution

Recalibrating the target lifetime can be achieved by tuning the range of the desirability function. This tightens the acceptable range of damage for the wind farm. Directly affecting the lifetime of the wind farm. Naturally, the range can be tightened or relaxed to achieve either of the solutions.

Unlike other optimization objective functions, often expressed in a particular unit, the desirability approach is set to a range from 0 to 1. This method removes the effectiveness of weights to steer the objective functions in a particular direction. However, adjusting the slope of the functions has a similar potential to steer the objective function into a specific direction.

The last method from the flow chart is to 'Reduce/increase damage' by tuning the damage desirability. This has proven to be a core component in the optimisation. The parameter is a functional tool to tune the desirability of the load with respect to the other loads within the wind farm.

Completely prioritising one objective involves removing the value function from the final optimisation objective. This approach focuses on combining multiple objective functions simultaneously while maintaining a high desirability for each outcome. Thus, ideally, it results in equally distributed loads over the wind farm without compromising the other objectives.

5.2.4 Redistribution of loads over the wind farm

The effectiveness of the desirability-based wind farm control strategy was evaluated on a 6-turbine layout using sector-averaged flow conditions. The case study targeted the redistribution of structural loads via wake steering, without compromising energy yield. All results were computed using the desirability approach.

Figure 5.5a shows the effect of tuning the desirability range, where the loading shows a trend to a more equally spread of loading across the different wind turbines for a narrowing of the desirability range, visible at the lower desirability range.

The desirability function was applied to each of the primary damage-equivalent load (DEL) channels and combined to form a scalar load objective per turbine.

The damage in the blade root out-of-plane (BROP) channel, a critical fatigue component under wake steering, was chosen to illustrate the effectiveness of the approach. Under a representative wind direction of 245° , the tuned desirability function led to a visible redistribution of loading: some turbines were relieved from excessive fatigue loading, while others took on a marginally increased share to balance the objective across the farm (Figure 5.5b). Despite optimizing for load, the yield was not compromised. Through the integrated control strategy, the highest loads could be reduced up to 7%.

(a) Optimisation trends of the structural objective.

(b) Optimised wake steering angles for redistributed loads.

Figure 5.5: Desirability-based wind farm optimisation results.

5.3 Graphical user interface

The wind farm control optimisation framework is implemented through an intuitive web-based graphical interface that enables users to interact with the optimisation algorithms and visualise results in real-time. This interface provides a comprehensive platform for setting up wind farm configurations, selecting optimisation objectives, and analyzing the resulting control strategies.

5.3.1 Wind farm setup and configuration

The interface begins with a wind farm setup section that allows users to define the spatial layout of turbines within the wind farm. Users can add individual turbines by specifying their x and y coordinates in meters, or alternatively, upload a CSV file containing multiple turbine positions for larger wind farms. The interface also

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Figure 5.6: Graphical user interface - Wind farm layout input field

provides pre-configured turbine layouts, including the Hollandse Kust Noord layout for SUDOCO-specific analysis, shown in figure 5.6.

The turbine positions are visualized in real-time using an interactive scatter plot, where each turbine is represented as a blue circular marker. The plot automatically scales to accommodate the wind farm dimensions and displays the total area coverage in square meters. This visual representation enables users to verify the spatial arrangement and identify potential wake interactions between turbines.

The core of the interface is the optimisation objective selection, which offers two primary control strategies:

- **Annual Energy Production (AEP) Optimisation:** This objective focuses on maximizing the total energy output of the wind farm through wake steering. The optimization algorithm computes optimal yaw angles for each turbine to minimize wake effects and maximize power capture. This approach is particularly effective for wind farms where energy production is the primary economic driver.
- **Load Optimization:** This objective implements the desirability-based approach described in Section 5.2, focusing on structural load redistribution across the wind farm. The optimization balances fatigue damage across different turbine components while maintaining acceptable energy production levels. This strategy is crucial for extending turbine lifetime and reducing maintenance costs.

Users can specify the prevailing wind conditions that influence the optimization:

- **Wind Speed:** Input field for wind speed in meters per second, with a default

Wind Farm Analysis

Run Yaw Optimization
Optimize turbine yaw angles to maximize Annual Energy Production (AEP)

Run Optimization

Optimization Settings

Optimization Objective:

- Annual Energy Production (AEP)**
Maximize power output and energy production
- Load Reduction**
Minimize structural loads and fatigue damage

Wind Conditions

Wind Speed (m/s):
Range: 1 - 25 m/s (recommended: 8-15 m/s)

Wind Direction (degrees):
0° = North, 90° = East, 180° = South, 270° = West

Figure 5.7: Graphical user interface - Optimization settings input field

value of 10 m/s. This parameter affects both the wake characteristics and the structural loading on turbine components.

- **Wind Direction:** Input field for wind direction in degrees, with a default value of 270° (westerly winds). The wind direction determines the wake patterns and the effectiveness of yaw-based wake steering strategies.

5.3.2 Result visualization

Upon initiating the optimization, the interface provides real-time feedback through a loading overlay and progress indicators. The optimization process typically takes several seconds to complete, depending on the number of turbines and the complexity of the wind farm layout. The results are presented through multiple visualization components, demonstrated in figure 5.8:

- **Optimization Summary:** A success message displays the number of turbines processed, the selected optimization objective, and the input wind conditions. This provides immediate confirmation that the optimization completed successfully.
- **Performance Metrics:** For AEP optimization, the interface shows the total power output with and without yaw optimization, along with the percentage improvement achieved. For load optimization, it displays the structural cost metrics and damage distribution across the wind farm.
- **Wind Farm Layout Visualization showing:**
 - The spatial distribution of turbines with optimized yaw angles is indicated by color coding

Figure 5.8: Graphical user interface - Result visualization in the graphical interface

- Performance summary statistics in an overlay box
- Wake Map Visualization: The interface also displays wake maps generated using PyWake simulations, showing the flow field around turbines and the effectiveness of wake steering strategies.

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6 Conclusion

The methods presented in this report outline a comprehensive framework for the holistic control of wind farms, integrating aerodynamic, structural, economic, and environmental considerations into a unified decision-making process. By combining a range of wind farm control techniques — including wake steering, the Helix approach, and axial induction control — with reduced-order structural load models, economic value functions, and environmental performance metrics, the framework supports operational strategies that optimise not only energy yield but also turbine lifetime, maintenance costs, and climate impact.

The integration of load surrogate models, particularly for floating offshore wind turbines, enables fast yet accurate estimation of fatigue damage, making it possible to incorporate lifetime effects directly into control optimisation. Economic models based on net present value provide a realistic assessment of profitability by linking control strategies to both revenue generation and operations and maintenance costs. Environmental models quantify both the carbon footprint and the emissions displaced by wind energy, ensuring that sustainability objectives are embedded in the optimisation process.

The framework further demonstrates how advanced optimisation strategies, such as economic lifetime-aware control and the desirability approach, can operationalise these models in a practical setting, balancing multiple objectives without compromising on energy production. The modularity of the approach allows for tailored applications, targeting yield maximisation or load redistribution, and ensures adaptability to evolving technology, market conditions, and regulatory requirements. Moreover, the inclusion of the environmental objective in one of the frameworks will be within the scope of work package 4.2.

Ultimately, the methods described here provide the foundation of the *Control Room of the Future* in which wind farms are operated with a truly holistic perspective. By explicitly capturing the interactions between technical performance, economic return, and environmental value, this integrated approach enables more informed, balanced, and future-proof operational decisions in the wind sector. The finalisation of the integration into optimised frameworks is the focus of *task 4.2 - Control room of the future (optimization)*, with outputs also feeding into related tasks, notably *task 5.3 - Co-design software tool* and *task 6.1 - Demonstration of the control room of the future*.

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A Preprint: Impact of reliability parameters on O&M cost and greenhouse gas emissions of offshore wind farms

On the following pages, the preprint of the EERA-Deepwind 2025 conference paper “Impact of reliability parameters on O&M cost and greenhouse gas emissions of offshore wind farms” is presented. The paper studies costs and emissions linked to varying component failure rates based on a specific O&M strategy following a time-series based approach. The tool is based on NREL’s “Windfarm Operations and Maintenance cost-Benefit Analysis Tool” (Hammond and Cooperman, 2022). The paper has been accepted by the conference editor and is planned to be published in Q4 of 2025. Once published, please refer to the final version of the article (IOP Publishing, Journal of Physics: Conference Series). This work is referenced in section 4.1.

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Impact of reliability parameters on O&M cost and greenhouse gas emissions of offshore wind farms

Moritz Gräfe¹, Samuel Kainz², Azélice Ludot¹, Vasilis Pettas¹,
Abhinav Anand², Carlo L. Bottasso²

¹DTU Wind and Energy Systems, Technical University of Denmark,
Frederiksborgvej 399, Roskilde 4000, Denmark

²Wind Energy Institute, Technische Universität München, Boltzmannstr. 15, 85748
Garching bei München, Germany

E-mail: mograf@dtu.dk

Abstract. This study examines the impact of reliability parameters of critical turbine components on offshore wind farm operation and maintenance (O&M) costs and related greenhouse gas (GhG) emissions. Employing a simulation-based sensitivity analysis, we assess how variations in reliability parameters influence key O&M metrics, including total costs, component-specific breakdowns, availability, intervention frequency, and vessel usage. The associated climate impact is quantified based on vessel fuel consumption and spare part usage. The analysis uses data from the offshore wind farm Lillgrund, incorporating extensive SCADA data and real environmental conditions. For a variation of the reliability parameters by $\pm 50\%$, results indicate a total variation of up to $\pm 15\%$ in operational expenditures in absolute terms and per MWh of produced electricity. The impact of failure rates on CO₂-equivalent emissions is observed to be around $\pm 50\%$ relative to the baseline case for individual components, highlighting the significant influence of reliability on both costs and emissions. These findings underscore the importance of incorporating O&M processes in assessing the GhG footprint of wind energy and establishing a link between turbine reliability and emissions. Additionally, research gaps are identified in understanding the relationship between load conditions and component failure behavior, particularly in the context of wind farm control strategies.

1 Introduction

As offshore wind energy has become a fundamental part of the energy system and wind farms (WFs) operate in increasingly competitive market environments, optimizing their operational performance is increasingly important. While operators aim to minimize costs and maximize revenue, society is particularly interested in reducing the greenhouse gas (GhG) footprint of electricity production.

Both aspects are strongly influenced by the operation and maintenance (O&M) phase of wind energy production. O&M costs typically account for approximately 30% of the total cost of offshore wind energy production, making it one of the primary cost drivers [1]. Similarly, O&M-related GhG emissions contribute significantly to the overall carbon footprint of offshore wind projects. As reported in [2], estimates of O&M-related emissions vary between 5% and 30%, depending on wind farm specific modeling assumptions and the level of detail considered. A recent study incorporating vessel-related emissions estimated that O&M activities contribute 28% of the total GhG emissions for a hypothetical 740 MW wind farm off the coast of the Netherlands [3].

The reliability of wind turbine components and the associated maintenance requirements are key factors in determining both costs and emissions, as they influence the frequency of component failures and the maintenance processes required to address them. Maintenance activities typically involve vessel transportation, specialized equipment, spare parts, and labor. Reliability is defined as the probability that a component does not fail within a given time interval, which is primarily determined by its failure rate - a statistical measure of the number of failures occurring over time.

Several factors can influence the failure rates of specific components. Wind farm control strategies, which address aerodynamic interactions between turbines or implement electrical control approaches such as power boosting, can introduce unexpected load patterns not considered in the original system design [4]. These altered load patterns may positively or negatively affect component reliability. Other contributing factors include design flaws, manufacturing defects, and improper installation. Determining failure rates remains challenging and is often associated with significant uncertainties. This study aims to improve understanding of these uncertainties and their impact on cost and GhG emissions estimations.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of existing studies and datasets quantifying the reliability of offshore wind turbine components. Section 3 introduces a workflow for assessing these impacts using operational data from an existing offshore wind farm and an O&M simulation tool that models the maintenance process in a time-marching manner. In section 4, the workflow is then demonstrated using the Lillgrund wind farm in the Baltic Sea as a case study. Finally, Section 5 discusses potential deviations from expected reliability and identifies key research gaps for future investigations.

2 Reliability data

The analysis of wind turbine reliability data presents several challenges, as outlined in the IEA Wind TCP Task 33 report [5] and supported by other studies. Operators often face difficulties in data collection, leading to poor data quality [6]. Additionally, the lack of standardized methods for O&M reporting, including systematic descriptions of affected components, failure modes, and failure definitions, further complicates reliability assessments [7]. Variability in failure classification by assembly adds another layer of complexity, making cross-study comparisons challenging [6, 8]. Limited collaboration among industry stakeholders, such as operators, manufacturers, and component suppliers further prevents data harmonization. Finally, ensuring that existing datasets accurately reflect modern turbine technology remains an ongoing challenge.

Thus, publicly available failure data for offshore wind farms is limited. While industry-owned databases offer insights into offshore risks, they are generally inaccessible due to confidentiality restrictions. In fact, open-access data is limited to three main sources, which are described in more detail below UK Round 1 offshore wind farms [9], Strathclyde database [10], and the reliability analysis of the Egmond aan Zee wind farm [11].

Under the “Offshore Wind Capital Grants Scheme,” UK Round 1 offshore wind farms were required to report operational data between 2004 and 2007. Feng et al. [9] analyzed these reports to extract lessons from early offshore wind operations, presenting findings on capacity factors, availability, and energy costs. Although failures and downtimes are discussed, no statistical failure analysis is provided. The dataset includes four wind farms, 120 turbines, totaling 300 MW and 270 operational years.

Operational reports from the Egmond aan Zee offshore wind farm in the Netherlands are available for the first three years of operation [11]. This wind farm consists of 36 Vestas V90-3MW wind turbines located 10–18 km offshore in the North Sea. The reports provide data on the number of stops caused by 13 sub-assemblies. However, the farm faced significant operational issues during its initial years, making these figures unrepresentative for use in a lifetime study.

Carroll et al. [10] published one of the most comprehensive datasets on reliability, referred to as the Strathclyde database, covering approximately 350 offshore wind turbines from a single manufacturer. The turbines have a nominal power between 2 MW and 4 MW and are between three and ten years old. What distinguishes this database from others is its detailed failure definitions, as well as insights into repair times, material costs, and the number of technicians required per subassembly. The study differentiates between minor and major repairs, as well as major replacements, providing comprehensive data for use in O&M cost models.

The limited availability of reliability data, particularly for specific turbine types and environmental conditions, introduces significant uncertainty in studies quantifying O&M costs and greenhouse gas emissions. Future research should prioritize improving access to operational data for statistical analysis and establishing links between technical, operational, and environmental factors affecting reliability.

3 Methodology

Figure 1 illustrates the methodology of this study, which is applied to the Lillgrund wind farm wind farm in the Baltic Sea. The characteristics of this wind farm, including layout, distance to port, vessel availability, metocean conditions, and turbine-specific power curves, are defined in Section 3.2. Reliability parameters for individual turbine components are derived from baseline values reported in the literature, with parameter variations applied as specified in Section 3.2. To account for seed-to-seed variability in individual simulation runs, 10 random realizations are generated for each simulation case.

The input parameters, including reliability parameters, simulation setup, and random seed, are then provided to the simulation tool WOMBAT [12], which models the operation and maintenance process, including failure occurrences, repair procedures, and turbine availability.

Figure 1: Methodology overview.

The modeled event chain begins with the sampling of failure times for each component and failure mode. When the simulation time reaches a component failure, the maintenance process is initiated. This process involves requesting the necessary resources (e.g., vessels, spare parts), assigning tasks to available resources, conducting maintenance activities, and restoring the operational status of the affected component. During this process, turbine downtime is accumulated, and O&M costs are tracked.

In WOMBAT, failure occurrences are modeled using a two-parameter Weibull distribution, which defines the probability of failure as a function of time. The scale parameter, λ , determines the failure rate, while the shape parameter, β , characterizes its variation over time: $\beta < 1$ indicates a decreasing failure rate, $\beta = 1$ represents a constant failure rate, and $\beta > 1$ corresponds to an increasing failure rate. A separate Weibull distribution is defined for each component and failure mode, with failure occurrences sampled independently. Each modeled component has three distinct failure modes - minor repair, major repair, and replacement - each characterized by specific parameters, including repair time, equipment requirements, and spare part costs. Lastly, the simulation results are postprocessed to determine the relevant key performance indicators. Electricity production is calculated using the site-specific metocean data time series, the availability time series from the O&M simulation, and the power curves of the individual turbines. The tracked O&M activities are translated into discounted OPEX via vessel-specific equipment rates, labor rates and failure-specific material costs.

3.1 O&M emissions

The GhG emissions related to the O&M activities over the plant lifetime are determined through post-processing of the WOMBAT model outputs. Three types of emission sources are considered: vessel fuel consumption, vessel production and maintenance, and spare part usage. To determine the emissions related to the fuel consumption during all O&M vessel activities, the total vessel hours for the involved vessel types are aggregated across their operational states transit, idle at site, and idle at port, with no emissions considered for the latter. The fuel consumption per hour for each vessel type and operational

state is estimated following the methodology proposed by ref. [13], except for the fuel rates of the Crew Transfer Vessel for transit, taken from ref. [14], and for idling at site that are scaled according to assumptions in ref. [13]. Fuel consumption is considered for both heavy fuel oil (HFO) and marine gas oil (MGO). The associated GhG emissions are then calculated using wake-to-wake CO₂-equivalent (CO₂eq) emission factors from ref. [15], ensuring a comprehensive assessment of the climate impact of O&M vessel operations over the plant lifetime.

The GhG emissions related to vessel production and maintenance are estimated with two reference datasets for barge production and barge maintenance extracted from the *ecoinvent* database v3.8 [16], using the ‘Allocation cut-off by classification’ system model. The aggregated total vessel usage hours are normalized with the assumed vessel lifetime of 25 years associated to the datasets, and subsequently multiplied with the climate change impact factor of the two reference activities, resulting in the GhG emissions related to the vessel production and maintenance. Due to lack of specific data, different vessel types are not distinguished.

Finally, the emissions associated with spare parts are calculated based on the life-cycle emissions of the original components from cradle to grave, excluding installation, which is already accounted for in vessel emissions. The emissions related to spare parts are allocated using a cost-based approach, where emissions are scaled by the ratio of material costs for repair and replacement activities to the costs of the original components. Both the life-cycle emissions and original component costs are determined using the DETECT toolchain [3], applied to the Lillgrund wind turbine specification.

3.2 Lillgrund case study

Lillgrund is Sweden’s largest offshore wind farm, located approximately 10 km off the southern coast of Sweden. It consists of 48 SWT 2.3 MW wind turbines, each with a rotor diameter of 93 m and a hub height of 65 m. The turbines are placed in a densely spaced layout, with an average inter-turbine distance of 3-5 rotor diameters (see Figure 2), leading to strong wake interactions.

Figure 2: Lillgrund wind farm layout.

To account for these wake effects, the power curve of each turbine was determined for discrete wind direction sectors using SCADA data provided by the operator for a three-year period (2019-2022). Specifically, one power curve was generated for each 30° sector for every turbine. In the post-processing stage, these sector-averaged power curves were input into the WOMBAT framework to calculate the overall power production of the wind farm based on hourly mean wind speed and wind direction.

The following procedure was employed to derive the sector-specific power curves. First, the raw high-frequency data were checked and resampled to 10-minute statistics. These statistics were then filtered using the FLASC [17] framework, applying filters on power, pitch, and rotor parameters to retain only normal operating conditions. From the filtered dataset, farm-wide wind speed and direction were obtained by averaging the free-stream turbines’ measurements for each wind direction. Using these aggregated wind speed and direction signals, the power curves for each turbine and sector were extracted, thereby incorporating operational wake losses. Figure 3 shows an example of such sector-averaged power curves.

Meteocean data for the considered 20-year operational period (2004-2023) were obtained from ERA5 reanalysis at the wind farm location, providing hourly time series of wind speed, wind direction, and significant wave height. Figure 4 illustrates the wind and wave conditions distributions for the site over the entire period.

Figure 3: Example of directional power curve extracted from SCADA data for the G05 turbine. Values are normalized due to confidentiality

(a) Windrose Lillgrund wind farm

(b) Wave height probability density function

Figure 4: Windrose and wave height probability density function.

The simulation parameters and settings for the O&M process simulation are set to reflect the characteristics of the Lillgrund wind farm. Where the detailed characteristics of the actual process parameters are unknown, the chosen values are based on assumptions. Table 1 summarizes the main simulation parameters.

Parameter	Value
Operational life	2004 to 2024
Discount rate	0.045
Workday	7h to 19h
Distance to port	10km
Annual service	60 h/turbine
Service vessel type	CTV

Table 1: Simulation parameters.

Pivotal for the cost and emission implication of reliability are the characteristics of vessels used for maintenance tasks. Table 2 summarizes the assumed parameters of the three vessel types, including their fuel consumption and their specific CO₂eq emissions.

Table 3 shows the baseline failure rates for the selected components considered in the case study. The reported baseline failure rates are taken from existing literature. Our study varies these failure rates with a range of -50% to +50% from the baseline values, while the failure rates of all components and failure modes varied simultaneously. The shape parameter of the failure probability distribution, β , is set to one, which represents a constant failure rate over time. It should be noted that different assumptions for β can lead to a significantly different total number of failures during the project lifetime. However, the

Vessel type	CTV	FSV	HLV
Nr. of vessels	2	1	2
Strategy	continuous	continuous	chartered ¹
Equipment rate [€/day]	2,410	13,082	206,550
Nr. of technicians	3	4	5
Labor rate [€/h]	75	75	75
Max. wind speed [m/s]	-	-	10
Max. wave height [m]	1.5	1.5	2
Speed [km/h]	37.0	22.2	20.4
Fuel type	HFO	MGO	MGO
Fuel emissions [kgCO ₂ eq/kg]	4.05	4.26	4.26
Fuel rate at port [kg/h]	0	0	0
Fuel rate travel [kg/h]	101.7	304.0	418.0
Fuel rate at site [kg/h]	38.1	114.0	156.8

¹ Chartered for 20 days as soon as three replacement requests accumulate. Foregoing mobilization time of 10 days with mobilization cost of 325,000€.

Table 2: Vessel parameters for crew transfer vessels (CTV), field-support vessels (FSV) and heavy lift vessels (HLV) based on ref. [12–14, 18, 19].

trends in costs and emissions from changing failure rates are not significantly modified for different shape parameters. All results are reported in steps of 10% deviation from the baseline failure rate. The failure rates are applied for all turbines in the wind farm uniformly.

Component	Minor ¹	Major ¹	Replacement ¹	Range
Blade	0.456	0.01	0.001	-50% to +50%
Pitch	0.824	0.179	0.001	
Yaw Bearing	0.162	0.006	0.001	
Gearbox	0.305	0.0338	0.042	
Generator	0.473	0.036	0.008	
Power Electronics	0.076	0.081	0.005	
Tower	0.092	0.089	0	

¹ Unit: *failures/turbine/year*

Table 3: Failure categories for selected components and baseline failure rates taken from [4, 10].

4 Results

Figure 5 presents the O&M costs throughout the project lifetime for the components specified in Table 3, considering failure rates ranging from -50% to +50% relative to the baseline (0%) failure rates. The individual bars represent the mean simulation results across all random seeds.

Costs are categorized into three groups: material costs, equipment costs, and labor costs. While an increase in failure rates affects all components, certain components contribute disproportionately to overall costs. These components are characterized by high baseline failure rates and high material and equipment costs. Under the assumptions of this study, and based on baseline failure rates derived from the literature, the gearbox accounts for the largest share of O&M costs. This is primarily due to the high cost of spare parts and the necessity of heavy-lift vessels for major replacements.

Figure 6 presents the total project OPEX and OPEX per unit of produced electricity for varying failure rates. The boxes represent the variability of results across all random seeds. The simulated total project OPEX ranges from approximately 145 M€ to 190 M€, corresponding to OPEX costs between 17 and 24 €/MWh across the full range of reliability variations. This highlights the potential for substantial increases or reductions in O&M costs as a result of changes in failure rates. The study demonstrates a total variation of approximately $\pm 15\%$ in operational expenditures, both in absolute terms and relative to the amount of electricity produced. While a 50% increase in all failure rates, potentially caused by

Figure 5: Component-wise break down of O&M costs.

Figure 6: Total OPEX (left) and OPEX per production (right).

factors such as changing load patterns, component quality, or installation issues, represents an extreme case, the results underscore the significance of failure rate variations in determining OPEX.

Figure 7 presents time-based and production-based availability as a function of changing failure rates. Time-based availability represents the proportion of technically available time relative to the total operational time, while production-based availability denotes the share of electricity produced relative to the theoretical maximum production without downtime. In contrast to the high variability observed in O&M costs, the sensitivity of availability to failure rates is relatively low, with variations of approximately $\pm 2\%$. It is important to note that these results assume the continuous availability of materials, equipment, and workforce. In practice, delays in spare part supply or vessel unavailability could lead to extended downtimes per failure, thereby amplifying the impact on availability.

Figure 8 illustrates the CO₂-equivalent emissions associated with different components over the range of failure rate variations. Emissions are categorized into vessel-related emissions (center) and material-related emissions (right). Vessel-related emissions include those resulting from fuel combustion and vessel operation and maintenance, while material-related emissions represent the life-cycle emissions of spare parts. Total emissions correspond to the sum of both categories.

The impact of failure rates on CO₂-equivalent emissions is observed to be approximately $\pm 50\%$ relative to the baseline case for individual components. Notably, the components responsible for the highest costs do not necessarily contribute the most to CO₂-equivalent emissions. While high costs are primarily driven by expensive materials, equipment, and labor (e.g., the gearbox), vessel-related emissions may be more significantly influenced by frequent but relatively low-cost minor repair activities.

This finding is further supported by Figure 9, which presents vessel-related emissions for the three vessel types used under varying failure rates. The results indicate that crew transfer vessels, primarily utilized for minor repair tasks, contribute the most to overall vessel emissions. In contrast, heavy-lift vessels and field support vessels, which are required for major repairs and replacements such as gearbox

Figure 7: Time-based availability (left) and production based availability (right).

Figure 8: Greenhouse gas emissions per component.

replacements, result in lower total CO₂-equivalent emissions.

5 Discussion

Our study demonstrates the general impact of varying failure rates on O&M costs and greenhouse gas emissions. However, the analysis relies on several assumptions regarding the characteristics of the maintenance process, associated costs, and emissions. More accurate data on the actual reliability of components in the investigated wind farm would be required to reduce uncertainty in the results. Therefore, the findings of this study should be interpreted as indicative of trends and orders of magnitude rather than precise predictions. Furthermore, this study does not investigate the underlying causes of deviations from expected component reliability.

Deviations from expected component reliability can arise from various root causes and physical phenomena. Potential causes of unexpected reliability issues include design flaws, manufacturing defects, quality control issues, and improper installation. In such cases, reliability deviations may occur independently of changes in the expected load patterns. Another source of reliability deviations may stem from variations in operational structural load patterns, which can lead to variations in fatigue damage accumulation and actuator wear and tear. These variations can be influenced by operational decisions such as the application of wind farm control strategies. Unlike conventional "greedy" control strategies that optimize individual turbine performance, wind farm control aims to optimize the operation of the entire wind farm. This is achieved through wind farm flow control, which mitigates aerodynamic interactions among turbines, and wind power plant control, which addresses electrical control objectives, such as grid service provision.

At the turbine level, wind farm control strategies include wake steering and induction control to minimize wake interactions, as well as power boosting and down-regulation to meet grid demands. These control actions can affect the load patterns on the individual components of each machine [20], potentially affecting reliability. However, these load pattern changes are not uniform across the wind farm. While some turbines may experience adverse effects, such as increased loads due to wake steering, downstream turbines may benefit from reduced wake interactions, resulting in more favorable load conditions.

Figure 9: Greenhouse gas emissions by considered vessel type.

From this discussion, we identify two key research gaps, particularly in the context of WF control:

1. The distribution of wind farm control-induced changes in turbine load patterns across wind farms is not sufficiently understood, described, or quantified.
2. The relationship between load conditions and reliability parameters remains largely unknown.

Future research should address both gaps. Ongoing work in this area includes developing wind farm response models that incorporate control actions and turbine flow interactions. Approaches based on fatigue damage accumulation or physical modeling of degradation mechanisms may provide further insights into the relationship between load conditions and reliability.

6 Conclusions

Our study presents a workflow for assessing the impact of reliability parameters on O&M costs and GhG emissions using existing publicly available tools, while accounting for site-specific conditions and the performance of an operating offshore wind farm. The results indicate a total variation of approximately $\pm 15\%$ in operational expenditures compared to the baseline values, both in absolute terms and per MWh of produced electricity. Additionally, the impact of failure rates on CO₂-equivalent emissions is observed to be around $\pm 50\%$ relative to the baseline case for individual components, demonstrating a substantial influence of failure rates on both costs and emissions.

These findings emphasize the importance of incorporating O&M processes into assessing the carbon footprint of wind energy and establish a link between turbine and component reliability and emissions. Enhancing the reliability of key components or adopting more sustainable maintenance strategies, such as the use of low-emission vessels, could significantly reduce emissions. Furthermore, we identify research gaps in understanding the relationship between load conditions and component failure behavior, particularly in the context of wind farm control activities.

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B Preprint: On the environmental value of wind farm control

On the following pages, the preprint of the EERA-Deepwind 2025 conference paper “On the environmental value of wind farm control” is presented. The paper introduces the SUDOCO method to calculate the marginal displacement factor of wind energy and demonstrates the method by means of an exemplary case study. The paper has been accepted by the conference editor and is planned to be published in Q4 of 2025. Once published, please refer to the final version of the article (IOP Publishing, Journal of Physics: Conference Series). This work is referenced in section 4.2.

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An initial study on the environmental value of wind farm control

Samuel Kainz¹, Annamaria Scherzl¹, Adrien Guilloré¹, Abhinav Anand¹ and Carlo L. Bottasso¹

¹Wind Energy Institute, Technische Universität München, Boltzmannstr. 15, 85748 Garching bei München, Germany

E-mail: samuel.kainz@tum.de

Abstract. The integration of wind energy into the electrical grid significantly reduces greenhouse gas emissions by displacing conventional power plants. This study presents a novel data-driven approach to quantify the environmental value of wind energy generation through the Marginal Displacement Factor (MDF), expressed in kgCO₂-equivalent per MWh. The MDF captures changes in emissions resulting from incremental variations in wind energy generation within an energy system, while accounting for the time-dependent fluctuations in grid emissions driven by the generation mix and demand-supply dynamics. Using the German energy system and the offshore wind farm Wikingen as a case study, results reveal substantial variability in the MDF and highlight the positive impact of wind energy on grid emission reduction. Furthermore, findings demonstrate that wake steering-based wind farm control for maximum power production can improve the environmental value of a wind farm within the same range as the increase in energy production.

1 Introduction

The energy transition is crucial for mitigating climate change, with renewable energy sources playing a central role in decarbonizing the electricity grid. Wind energy, in particular, is a key driver of this shift due to its significantly lower carbon footprint compared to conventional generation technologies [1, 2]. As the energy mix becomes more diverse, including both fossil-based and renewable sources along with storage technologies and variable demand, grid emissions fluctuate over time. These fluctuations are directly influenced by the generation mix, which is shaped by factors such as power generation, imports and exports, and market imbalances. Consequently, grid emissions are not constant but vary based on supply-demand dynamics, market conditions, and power flows within the grid.

In the dynamic and interconnected energy systems of today, clean generation technologies often displace other – primarily fossil fuel-based – power plants, depending on the operational state of the system. The changes in grid greenhouse gas emissions resulting from an incremental increase in energy produced by a displacing technology is referred to as the Marginal Displacement Factor (MDF), expressed in kilograms of carbon dioxide equivalent per megawatt-hour produced (kgCO₂e/MWh). Similarly, the additional grid emissions generated per incremental increase in demand is termed the Marginal Emission Factor (MEF), measured in the same units as MDF [2]. The determination of MEF and MDF requires the identification of the emissions related to the generators operating at the margin, i.e., those that actively adjust their output to maintain grid balance. To this end, several studies have applied merit order-based approaches, primarily aiming at the estimation of the MEF. Some derived the merit order from historical data [3, 4] or power plant activation criteria [5], while others, such as ref. [6], extended this approach to future energy systems, requiring a detailed modeling of all power plants and their interdependencies.

Figure 1: The environmental value of wind farm control: by changing the wind farm power output, wind farm control can marginally alter the generation mix in the connected energy system, ultimately affecting the total grid emissions.

Identifying the marginal generators is a highly complex and market-dependent problem, which is influenced by regulations, policies, dispatch schedules, cross-border transfers, and real-time grid conditions. A data-driven approach offers an effective and straightforward solution, as it implicitly accounts for all the relevant driving factors from both markets and the grid. By capturing these dynamics in a statistical sense, a data-driven model can predict the most likely MEF and MDFs, based on the operational state of the considered energy system. Therefore, previous research has predominantly relied on data-driven approaches, often employing linear regression models. An early study [7] used simple regression analysis to map system emissions to a single system state variable. Later works [2, 8] refined this approach by incorporating additional system variables and accounting for physical limitations of power plants. Ref. [9] further extended the linear regression approach to account for electricity imports and exports. A more recent study [10] applied machine learning to improve the temporal resolution of MEF estimation, but was constrained to a limited set of system state variables in a highly renewable energy system and focused solely on the MEF. In summary, previous research has either relied on identifying the marginal generators within market-specific merit orders – which requires data that is not publicly available and involves large physical models with numerous assumptions – or has been limited to a narrow set of system state variables, to specific case studies, and with a primary focus on the MEF.

To address these limitations, this work introduces a data-driven approach with a general formulation to calculate both the MEF and the MDFs for all considered generation technologies, using standard system data often made publicly available by transmission system operators. The study focuses on the MDF of wind energy and the effects of wind farm control (WFC) on grid emission in particular. Advancements in WFC technologies have significantly improved the ability of wind power plants to generate and deliver additional electricity to the grid, depending on the wind resource availability. This capability enables the estimation of the additional displaced grid emissions attributable to WFC, thereby allowing for a more explicit quantification of the environmental value of WFC, as visualized in Fig. 1. Once quantified, the time-varying nature of the environmental value of WFC could be leveraged to maximize its impact by increasing the power output of the wind farm during time periods when the grid is predominantly supplied by higher-emission power plants. Furthermore, the environmental value of WFC could be assessed alongside its economic value, considering fluctuating energy market conditions and effects of WFC on the structural health of wind turbine components, to develop a multi-objective control strategy that balances economic and environmental sustainability. It is also possible that, in the future, the displacement of carbon-emitting plants might be incentivized, thereby providing an additional revenue stream. While this paper does not directly explore these aspects, the developed method and results provide a foundation for future research on value-based WFC strategy optimization.

2 Methodology

2.1 Time series of emissions

First, the total emissions occurring in the considered energy system are determined from time series. In this study, the scope of an energy system is defined to correspond to the boundaries of a country. However, the approach is more general and can be applied to regions with lower or higher granularity, such as control areas or bilateral market zones.

Since electricity grids are characterised by a high level of interconnectivity, the total emissions E for different operational states of an energy system at a given time t depend on the emissions due to electricity generation within the country as well as the emissions from electricity imports and exports:

$$E(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_{tech}} e_k P_k^{gen}(t) + \sum_{nc=1}^{N_{nc}} e_{nc}(t) P_{nc}^{imp}(t) - e_{int}(t) \sum_{nc=1}^{N_{nc}} P_{nc}^{exp}(t). \quad (1)$$

Here, N_{tech} denotes the number of generation technologies operating within the country, P_k^{gen} the aggregated power production from a particular generation technology k , e_k the technology-specific emission intensity, P_{nc}^{imp} the electricity imported from N_{nc} neighbouring countries, e_{nc} the average emission intensity of the respective neighbouring country, P_{nc}^{exp} the electricity exported to a given neighbouring country nc , and e_{int} the average emission intensity due to production within the country under consideration.

The average emission intensity of a neighbouring country e_{nc} at a given time instant t is calculated as

$$e_{nc}(t) = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{N_{tech}^{nc}} e_k P_k^{gen}(t)}{\sum_{k=1}^{N_{tech}^{nc}} P_k^{gen}(t)}, \quad (2)$$

where N_{tech}^{nc} denotes the number of generation technology in the neighbouring country nc .

Similarly, the average emission intensity due to production within the country under consideration e_{int} is calculated as

$$e_{int}(t) = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{N_{tech}} e_k P_k^{gen}(t)}{\sum_{k=1}^{N_{tech}} P_k^{gen}(t)}. \quad (3)$$

To simplify the notation, the dependency on time t is omitted in the following.

2.2 Marginal displacement vector

As shown in the previous section, the time-varying overall system emissions depend on the generation mix of the considered country as well as the imports and exports from the neighbouring countries. The electricity supply, in turn, depends on the electricity demand within the country. Therefore, the total system emissions E can be expressed as

$$E = f(\underline{p}), \quad (4)$$

where \underline{p} is a column vector of length p containing the system state variables demand D , all various generation technologies within the grid such as wind energy P_w , photovoltaic P_s , gas, coal, nuclear, etc., and imports P_{imp} and exports P_{exp} to and from neighbouring countries:

$$\underline{p} = [D, P_w, P_s, \dots, P_{imp}, P_{exp}]^T. \quad (5)$$

Next, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is used to reduce the dimensionality of the problem and decouple the features by transforming them into a set of uncorrelated principal components, minimizing interdependencies while retaining the most significant variance in the data. This can be written as

$$\underline{p} - \underline{p}_m = \mathbf{T}\Theta, \quad (6)$$

where \underline{p}_m is the mean of \underline{p} , ensuring data centering for PCA, Θ is the vector of length θ containing the principal components, and \mathbf{T} is a transformation of coordinates with dimension $p \times \theta$, which is numerically calculated using the Matlab implementation of PCA [11]. An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) Y , described in detail in the next section, is used to map the principal components to the total system emissions. Therefore, Eq. (4) can be rewritten as:

$$E = Y(\Theta). \quad (7)$$

The changes in system emissions with respect to infinitesimal changes in the system state variables can be determined via the partial derivative of Eq. (7), resulting in the definition of the marginal displacement $\delta e = -\delta E$, which writes

$$\delta e = - \left(\frac{\partial Y}{\partial \Theta} \right)^\top \delta \Theta. \quad (8)$$

The negative sign ensures that marginal displacements are positive when emissions are displaced and negative when additional emissions are generated in the considered energy system.

Next, the grid balance constraint is introduced, ensuring that changes in demand are always met by supply and vice versa:

$$\underline{v}^\top \delta \underline{p} = \underline{n}^\top \delta \underline{p} = 0, \quad (9)$$

with \underline{v} being a column vector of length p containing a value of -1 at the position occupied by demand in vector \underline{p} and 1s elsewhere, and \underline{n} being the unit vector of \underline{v} :

$$\underline{v} = [-1, 1, 1, \dots, 1]^\top, \quad \underline{n} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{p}} \underline{v}, \quad \underline{n}^\top \underline{n} = \underline{1}. \quad (10-12)$$

Given an arbitrary variation $\delta \underline{p}$, the corresponding variation that satisfies the grid balance constraint writes

$$\delta \underline{p}^* = (\mathbf{I} - \underline{n} \underline{n}^\top) \delta \underline{p}. \quad (13)$$

Combining Eq. (6), (8) and (13) leads to the definition of the marginal displacement vector:

$$\frac{\partial e}{\partial \underline{p}} = - \left(\frac{\partial Y}{\partial \Theta} \right)^\top \mathbf{T}^\top (\mathbf{I} - \underline{n} \underline{n}^\top). \quad (14)$$

This marginal displacement vector contains the MEF at the location of D in vector \underline{p} , and the MDFs for the respective generating technologies as well as imports and exports at their respective positions in \underline{p} .

The derivatives of the emission function with respect to the principal components, noted

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial \Theta} = \left[\frac{\partial Y}{\partial \Theta_1}, \frac{\partial Y}{\partial \Theta_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial Y}{\partial \Theta_\Theta} \right]^\top, \quad (15)$$

are calculated numerically using central finite differences applied to the trained ANN:

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial \Theta_i} = \frac{Y(\Theta_i + \Delta \Theta_i) - Y(\Theta_i - \Delta \Theta_i)}{2 \Delta \Theta_i}. \quad (16)$$

Notice that the principal components are orthogonal to each other and therefore represent independent features. The step size $\Delta \Theta_i$ is determined by multiplying the relative step width w with the quantile span between the 2.5% quantile $Q_{2.5}$ and the 97.5% quantile $Q_{97.5}$ of the respective principal components:

$$\Delta \Theta_i = w (Q_{\Theta_i, 97.5} - Q_{\Theta_i, 2.5}). \quad (17)$$

2.3 Artificial neural network for emission prediction

An ANN is trained to predict the grid emissions for a given set of system state variables at a specific time. The ANN is implemented in Matlab [12] as a shallow feed-forward network with one hidden layer containing 350 neurons. The network is trained for 500 epochs using the Levenberg-Marquardt optimization algorithm based on default values [12], with hyperbolic tangent activation functions in both the hidden layers and the output layer. The dataset is split into 65% for training, 20% for validation, and 15% for testing. The model performance is evaluated using the R^2 score, where a value of 1 indicates perfect correlation between predicted and actual values, and the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), which quantifies the average prediction error in the same units as the target variable. The inputs and target datasets are normalized to a range between 0 and 1 to improve training stability and performance.

The number of neurons and epochs are selected such that the ANN predictions are robust not only for the target function but also for its derivatives, as required for the calculation of the MDF according to Eq. (14). Figure 2 presents the results of a parametric study exploring different neuron and epoch configurations using the dataset described in the *Results* section. The network performance, along with the mean and standard deviation (SD) of both total system emissions and the MDF of wind, are used

Figure 2: Results of the parametric study investigating the effects of varying number of neurons and epochs on the ANN performance (RMSE of the system emissions), ANN target prediction in terms of mean and standard deviation of the system emissions, and prediction of the MDF of wind in terms of mean and standard deviation. The red cross marks the selected configuration for the case study.

as performance indicators. The final configuration is manually chosen as a trade-off between robustness, computational efficiency, and minimizing the risk of overfitting. As the MDF exhibits significant sensitivity to the selected training function, the impact of the training function choice, along with the propagation of uncertainties in data and model parameters, will be investigated in a follow-up study.

The target grid emissions are calculated according to Eq. (1). Table 1 lists the final set of input variables for the ANN. To simplify the input features, imports and exports are aggregated as total net imports and total net exports across all neighboring countries. This differs from the approach used to calculate the ANN target emissions, where imports and exports are treated separately for each neighboring country, reducing complexity and computational demand while still capturing essential system dynamics. Time series data for electricity generation, imports, and exports are taken from the open-source ENTSO-E Transparency Platform [13]. Electricity demand is computed as the net sum of generation, imports, and exports. Table 1 provides the corresponding ENTSO-E data tags for each input variable. Each dataset is downloaded at the highest available frequency and subsequently resampled to quarter-hourly time steps.

Emission intensities for the considered technologies are sourced from the ecoinvent database v3.7.1 [1], using the ‘Allocation cut-off by classification’ system model. Germany is selected as the geographic scope, serving as a representative reference for emission intensities across the studied European countries. Emission intensities are adjusted to include only operational emissions of the generating technologies, as only these can be displaced in real-time on the electrical grid. On the other hand, life-cycle emissions linked to infrastructure such as powerplants, transmission or distribution grids are omitted because they cannot be displaced by a change in wind power generation. Transmission and distribution losses are implicitly included in the original datasets.

2.4 Wind farm performance and control optimization

The simulation software FLORIS [14] is used to calculate both the baseline power production and the increased power potential achieved through wake steering. Velocity deficits are calculated using the Jensen model [15] with a wake decay coefficient of 0.05 and are combined via root-sum-square superposition. Wake deflections are determined using the Jiménez model [16] with default parameters. The Serial-Refine method [17] is applied to generate look-up tables with optimized yaw angles ranging from -30° to $+30^\circ$ for each turbine, considering all possible combinations of ambient wind speed and wind direction. Discretization is set to 1 m/s for wind speed, 1° for main inflow directions, and 2.5° for other directions. Optimum yaw angles are then linearly interpolated to accommodate any arbitrary combination of wind speed and direction within the operational regime.

3 Results

3.1 Marginal displacement factor in Germany

As a first step, the proposed method for calculating the MDF of wind is applied to the German energy system, using time series data from 2021 and 2022. After performing PCA, five principal components are retained, capturing more than 97% of the total initial variance. Half of the shuffled dataset is used

ANN Feature	Column(s) in ENTSO-E dataset [13]	ecoinvent base activity [1] (adapted for direct operational emissions only)	Emission Factor (kgCO _{2e} /MWh)
Demand	Domestic supply ¹	-	acc. to Eq. (1) ²
Wind	Wind Offshore ³	electricity prod., wind, 1-3MW turbine, offshore	0.2
	Wind Onshore ³	electricity prod., wind, 1-3MW turbine, onshore	0.2
Solar	Solar ³	electricity prod., photovoltaic, 570kWp open ground	0.0
Lignite	Fossil Brown coal / Lignite ³	electricity prod., lignite	1221.9
Hard coal	Fossil Hard coal ³	electricity prod., hard coal	1049.6
Oil	Fossil Oil ³	electricity prod., oil	846.5
Gas	Fossil Gas ³	electricity prod., natural gas, conv. power plant	421.8
Nuclear	Nuclear ³	electricity prod., nuclear, pressure water reactor	4.4
Hydro	Hydro Pumped Storage ³	electricity prod., hydro, pumped storage	883.1
	Hydro Run-of-river ³	electricity prod., hydro, run-of-river	0.0
Other RE	Hydro Water Reservoir ³	electricity prod., hydro, reservoir, non-alpine region	44.8
	Geothermal ³	electricity prod., deep geothermal	0.0
	Marine ³	average of used renewable emission factors	122.6
	Other renewable ³	average of used renewable emission factors	122.6
Other Conv.	Biomass ³	heat and power co-generation, wood chips, 6667 kW	52.6
	Waste ³	zero since emissions are allocated to waste producer	0.0
	Other ³	average of used conventional emission factors	885.0
	Fossil Coal-derived gas ³	average of used conventional emission factors	885.0
Imports	Fossil Oil shale ³	average of used conventional emission factors	885.0
	Fossil Peat ³	average of used conventional emission factors	885.0
	Neighbors to Germany ⁴	-	acc. to Eq. (2)
Exports	Germany to neighbors ⁴	-	acc. to Eq. (3)

¹ Electricity demand is computed as the net sum of inland generation, imports, and exports.

² The total emissions E derived from Eq. (1) are divided by the electricity demand.

³ ENTSO-E dataset: Actual Generation per Production Type

⁴ ENTSO-E dataset: Cross-Border Physical Flow

Table 1: Features of the artificial neural network, used ENTSO-E datasets with associated specifications [13], as well as emission factors and their corresponding base activities from the ecoinvent database [1].

for training the ANN, achieving R^2 scores of 0.996 for training and 0.995 for testing. The full time series is used for the statistical analysis of the MDF, while two representative weeks – one in winter and one in summer – are selected for demonstration purposes. However, given the nature of the underlying open-source database [13], this analysis can easily be extended to any country, market, or control zone within the European Union using data from the past ten years.

The step width w required for Eq. (17) is determined first. Figure 3 illustrates the effect of varying the step width on the mean and SD of the MDF of wind. As expected, these metrics converge for sufficiently small step widths. Within this study, the proposed method is intended to analyze the environmental value of both the baseline production and the effects of WFC in a 350 MW wind farm, as described in the next section. Therefore, the step width is determined by perturbing the wind energy production in the studied time series by the rated power of the wind farm, calculating the resulting changes in the principal components, and comparing them with the step size defined in Eq. (17). This process yields a maximum allowed step width of 1.51%, which, as shown in Fig. 3, is considered to be sufficiently small.

Figure 3: Impact of the step width w on the mean and standard deviation of the MDF of wind. A dashed line indicates the step width selected for the case study.

Figure 4: Histogram distributions of MEF and MDFs for the 10 main considered features in Germany during 2021 and 2022. The mean values are indicated by orange dashed lines.

While this analysis primarily focuses on the MDF of wind energy, the proposed method is capable of predicting the MEF and the MDF for all features involved. Accordingly, Fig. 4 presents the histograms and mean values for the MEF and MDF distributions of the 10 most significant features. Wind, solar, and nuclear power generally exhibit positive MDFs, indicating a beneficial impact on the grid emissions. In contrast, increased demand, as well as increased hard coal and lignite generation, typically worsen the environmental performance of the grid. Hydropower, gas, imports, and exports have either positive or negative environmental impacts, depending on the other system state variables. The widespread variation in the MDF distributions underscores the importance of accounting for their time-dependent nature when assessing the environmental value of these technologies at a specific moment. The MDF of wind has an average value of 441.1 kgCO₂e/MWh, with a 99% data-based confidence interval ranging from -88.6 to 1,068.7 kgCO₂e/MWh. This indicates that wind energy is displacing various combinations of generators across most of the studied generational technologies as listed in Table 1, with an average impact comparable with the emission factor of gas power plants. However, wind energy can sometimes cause additional emissions in the grid when the MDF of wind is negative, which may be either associated with phenomena like congestion management requiring fossil power plants for compensation or numerical errors in the ANN, warranting further research. The fact that the other MDF distributions also fall within the physically plausible ranges of the studied generation technologies – except for a few outliers due to numerical errors – supports the validity of the proposed method for calculating MDFs.

As expected, wind energy generation primarily causes a positive impact on the environmental performance of the grid, although the magnitude of this effect is highly time-dependent. To explore this further, Fig. 5 presents two sample time series from Germany in 2022, illustrating the generation mix, imports and exports, total system emissions, and MDF of wind during two exemplary weeks in summer and winter, respectively. The winter week is characterised by strong wind but limited solar availability, significant gas-fired generation, and substantial electricity exports. In contrast, the summer week exhibits a slightly lower demand, less wind but abundant solar resources, and fluctuating shifts between net imports and exports due to solar variability. In both cases, the total system emissions highly depend on the availability of wind and solar resources. Notably, the system emissions predicted by the ANN align well with those calculated using Eq. (1), reinforcing the previously reported high R² performance indices.

The MDF of wind exhibits significant variability, ranging from -53.9 to 1,215.1 kgCO₂e/MWh in the exemplary winter week, with a weekly average of 555.1 kgCO₂e/MWh. In the summer week, values range from -237.1 to 1089.4 kgCO₂e/MWh, with an average of 426.4 kgCO₂e/MWh. These findings align with the previously presented statistical analysis of the full two-year time series, but suggest that MDF values tend to be higher in winter. Additionally, the MDF of wind shows distinct daily fluctuations, often reaching its lowest values around noon and peaking around midnight. Pronounced shifts seem to occur during periods of rapid changes in solar and wind energy generation.

Figure 5: Time series of supply, demand, calculated and predicted system emissions, and the MDF of wind for two exemplary weeks in winter (left) and summer (right) in Germany in 2022.

3.2 Displaced emissions through wind farm control

The environmental value of both the baseline performance of a wind farm and the effects of WFC is evaluated using the offshore wind farm Wikinger [18] for the year 2022 as a case study. Wikinger was commissioned in 2017, is located in the Baltic Sea, and is connected to the German electricity grid. The wind farm consists of 70 turbines with a total nominal capacity of 350 MW, and is modeled in FLORIS, as described in Sect. 2.4. Due to limited access to the actual turbine performance curves, the Adwen AD5-135 turbines are replaced with NREL 5-MW Reference Turbines [19], which have the same rated power and a similar rotor diameter. The hub height is set to its actual value of 97.5 m. Hourly inflow time series are obtained from ERA5 [20], with wind speed scaled to hub height using the power law with the alpha exponent determined for each time step based on the reference wind speeds at a height of 10 m and 100 m, respectively. The turbine positions are extracted from OpenStreetMap data [21].

As shown in Fig. 6, the farm layout is well-suited for enhancing total power output through yaw-optimized wake steering. Over the course of 2022, the calculated baseline energy production of 1400.8 GWh can be increased by 3.15% through WFC using wake steering. The associated grid emissions displaced by Wikinger are determined by multiplying the time series of the wind farm power production with the corresponding values for MDF of wind. Accordingly, Wikinger displaced 686.6 MtCO₂e in 2022, with a potential increase of 2.99% through wake steering. On average, the electricity displaced by Wikinger corresponds to emissions of 490.3 kgCO₂e/MWh. This value is 25 to 77 times higher than the carbon footprint of typical offshore wind farms [22], underscoring the significant role of wind energy in reducing the carbon intensity of the connected energy system.

Finally, Fig. 7 illustrates the wind farm power production and the corresponding displaced grid emissions, both with and without wake steering, for the same two exemplary weeks analyzed previously. The respective weekly means are indicated by dashed lines. In both weeks, the baseline production of

Figure 6: Flow field at the Wiking wind farm for the main inflow direction and mean wind speed, shown for (a) the baseline scenario, and (b) the wake steering scenario, visualized with FLORIS [14].

Wiking fluctuates significantly between zero and nominal capacity due to wind variability, with higher average power outputs in the winter week due to better resource availability. The trend in displaced grid emissions generally follows the power production but exhibits notable deviations due to the pronounced variability of the MDF of wind, as discussed earlier. This effect is particularly evident during periods of rated power production, where the power output remains constant while the displaced grid emissions fluctuate considerably. Similarly, the trends in additional power production and increased displaced emissions due to wake steering follow similar patterns, while relative changes sometimes differ significantly. Gains of up to 38.3 MW for power and 14.8 tCO₂e/h for emissions displacements are observed, with their peaks occurring at different times. On average, wake steering yields higher benefits in the summer week, as the wind farm operates less frequently at rated power, leaving more room for incrementing the power output when sufficient wind is available. Notably, at two instances, the wind farm production slightly increases the grid emissions due to a negative MDF of wind. This effect could be mitigated through control actions, such as shutting down turbines at such moments. Further investigation into these negative values and their impact on control strategies will be subjects of future research.

4 Conclusion

This paper presented a novel data-driven method for calculating the time-varying grid emission displacements related to demand, generation technologies, and import and exports of a given country, control or market zone, with a particular focus on the MDF of wind energy. The approach was demonstrated for the German energy system in the years 2021 and 2022. The environmental performance of an offshore wind farm connected to the German electricity grid was evaluated both for its baseline operation and for potential improvements through wake steering-based WFC. Overall, wind energy generation significantly reduces grid emissions, with average emission displacements comparable to the emission factor of gas power plants. The case study of the Wiking offshore wind farm showed that wake steering for maximum power production could enhance the environmental performance of the farm by approximately 3%, which is within the range of the observed increases in energy yield. However, the time-dependent nature of the MDF of wind leads to considerable fluctuations in the environmental performance of wind farms, with displaced emissions spanning the entire portfolio of typical generation technologies. Future work will focus on optimizing operational strategies to maximize the environmental benefits. Additionally, trade-offs involving energy yield, fatigue loads, reliability, and economic revenue will be explored, along with the simultaneous optimization of environmental-aware control strategies and layout of a wind farm.

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Figure 7: Time series of the baseline power generation and displaced emissions at Wikinger, and additional benefit from wake steering, for two exemplary weeks in winter (left) and summer (right) in 2022.

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